

INTERNATIONAL SCIENCE STUDENTS' POST-SECONDARY EXPERIENCES IN CANADA
AND IN WEST AFRICA: THE COHERENCE BETWEEN TEACHING AND LEARNING.

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Table of Contents

ABSTRACT	iii
DEDICATION	iv
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	v
CHAPTER 1	
INTRODUCTION	5
BACKGROUND	9
CHAPTER 2 - LITERATURE REVIEW	
2.0 OVERVIEW	12
2.1 CULTURAL DIFFERENCES AND CONFLICTS	13
2.1.1 EMOTIONAL STRESS IN LEARNING	15
2.1.2 VALUE PATTERNS	16
2.2 CULTURAL COMPETENCE	17
2.3 ACCEPTANCES AND TOLERANCE	19
2.4 CONFLICT WITH TECHNOLOGY	21
2.4.1 TECHNOLOGY AS A SOCIAL PROCESS	23
CHAPTER 3 - METHODOLOGIES AND STRATEGIES	
3.0 OVERVIEW	25
3.1 TOOLS FOR DATA COLLECTION AND SETTING ...	28
3.2 PARTICIPANTS PROFILE	32
3.3 DESCRIPTION OF PARTICIPANTS	35
3.4 INTERVIEW QUESTIONS AND DESIGN PROCESS	35
3.4.1 INTERVIEW GUIDED QUESTIONS	36
CHAPTER 4 – FINDINGS	
4.0 OVERVIEW	38
4.1 TOMMY	40
4.2 VERO	42
4.3 SKEMEH	42
4.4 TENI	44
4.5 PROFESSOR MAY	46
CHAPTER 5 - DISCUSSIONS OF THE FINDINGS	
5.0 OVERVIEW	51
5.1 THEME 1: EDUCATORS’ AND LEARNERS’ COMMITMENT	53

5.2 THEME 2: RESOURCES AND HANDS-ON EXPERIENCE (LEARNERS)	54
5.3 THEME 3: EDUCATORS' AND LEARNERS' CULTURAL DIFFERENCES	57
5.4 THEME 4: CULTURAL CAPITAL AND A VOICE IN ACCOUNTABILITY	58
5.5 THEME 5: MARGINALIZING AND DISCONNECTEDNESS	60
 CHAPTER 6 - INFERENCES AND CONCLUSIONS	
6.0 INFERENCES.....	63
6.1 RECOMMENDATION FOR POLICY AND PRACTICE	65
6.2 FUTURE DIRECTIONS AND RECOMMENDED FOR STUDENTS SUCCESS	69
6.3 IMPLICATION FOR THE RESEARCH AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS	70
REFERENCES	75
 APPENDICES	
APPENDIX A: SAMPLE - QUESTIONS AND ANSWERS WITH AN INTERVIEW PARTICIPANT	78
APPENDIX B: PHYSICS ASSIGNMENT SCRIPTS AND COURSE OUTLINES	89
APPENDIX C: INFORMED CONSENT FORM	90

Abstract

West African science students studying in Canadian post-secondary educational institutions encounter a host of challenges. It is important to learn more about these challenges students face in the pedagogical process, and how these challenges might be connected to paradigm shifts in both the teaching and learning processes that students encounter in new educational milieus. For example, problem solving is taught and learned in different ways in different learning environments.

I will attempt to find out post-secondary students' ability to answer problem-solving questions in science (physics) and examine if a different learning environment has an effect on their performance levels. I will do this by making reference to my past physics assignment scripts from my previous graduate studies. This study focuses on the problems related to the question of how to teach students from diverse cultural backgrounds so they experience the same academic achievement in the sciences as local students.

There is discussion of factors that impede both foreign local Canadian science students' transition in their post-secondary studies. A student's ability to overcome anxiety and stress-related disorders are some of the factors discussed. In this research I employed grounded theory in conducting interviews and used the collected interview data of individuals' experiences to make reference to my auto-ethnography. The key findings from the study of the experiences of West African science students are connected to themes such as; educators and learners commitment, resources and hands-on-experience, cultural differences, voice and accountability, and marginalization and disconnectedness.

Dedication

This manuscript is presented as a guide to educate all West African science students in Canada, particularly the Ghanaian science students for the commonness of the struggle we share in pursue of Higher Education in Canada and elsewhere.

I also dedicate it to *D/Insp. Odame, Appiah (Daddy)* earnest support without which the completion of this thesis could have been very difficult.

Acknowledgement

As I position myself as an active voice to a minority group, to speak to somebody, I have also learnt my hard lessons resilience and perseverance. These lessons include commitment, which transcends feelings. Through the many encounters in my experiences, I have the singular honor to acknowledge Professor Francis Ahia of University of Toronto who earnestly stood with me as I faced the strife in my academic pursuit in my previous graduate studies in physics and who still counsels me today. Also thanks to my beautiful wife Sarah for her support for boosting my moral. Honey, you are sweet and I love you. Thanks also to Professor Alsop (my research supervisor) and all members of my supervisory team who worked with me for success. Thanks also to the participants who supported me through interviews in making this research possible. Thank you all and I care.

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In the process of adjusting to a new culture, what are some of the emerging factors that will impede or facilitate the success of these science students both academically and socially as they pursue higher education in Canada? Many international science students encounter challenges in their post-secondary studies when they are met with new, and often alien, scholarly traditions in their post secondary institution in their new country. This “transition process” can be personally difficult, as it requires the student to adapt to customs and cultures of the receiving country, and to deal with the loss of the familiar customs and cultures in their originating country. In this research project I highlight the background and rationale of the research in the first chapter, and the second chapter discuss some of the selected literature works of writers. The third chapter details the methodology used in compiling and completing this research whereas chapter four look at some of the excerpts of the participants’ discussions. The fifth chapter lists and discusses inferences and pertinent themes that were drawn from informants’ interviews. In the sixth chapter I seek to use the themes deduced in chapter five to answer the research questions raised in chapter one.

Studies have shown that in many cases the acculturation stage in the transition processes did not go as smoothly as expected due to a host of factors including the participants’ personal “cultural baggage” (Hofstede, 1991 & 1997; Riley, 2005; Russell, 2005; and Dzama, 1999). In many cases, students have to adjust to specific differences in how discipline is delivered in different cultures and countries. The experiences of West African science students’ offer points of discussion for this research. Other author’s speculation that Blacks perform poorly in science is stereotypical in the sense that it labels and further compounds the reasons leading to the performance gap (Dzama, 1999). Others coin such notions differently, which would thus create

the perception that associates these experiences as individual problem. This research is specifically about science students' experiences in studying in the culturally alienated amalgamated Canadian higher educational system and focuses on the role cultural background plays in the experiences of West African science students.

This research builds on the work of Hofstede (1991 & 1997) and Riley (2005). I define experiences to include the paradigm shifts which individuals encounter in their academic and social lives. A counter-culture approach to advocate for ideas in education is employed as a framework to analyze resonating themes and arguments necessary for promoting the interest and success of West African science students (Freire, 2006, 2005 & 1970; Riley, 2005). The counter-culture approach, according to Freire (2006), should seek to build and foster good students-teacher relationships. Such relationships will help to sustain both educators' and learners' successes. I define "emancipation" as validating the ethnographic cultural practices of other groups of people. According to Giltrow (2002), ethnography is scholarly emancipatory writing that is developed from first-hand observations of social groups.

Little is written about West African science students' experiences in the context of Canadian Higher Education, but in talking to four students from the sub-region, it was clear that they were dissatisfied with the marks they received in course assignments. This study offers comment on what may be the root causes of the attainment of such poor marks. The participants angrily expressed the way marks have been awarded to them, even though they deserved to receive higher grades than their white counter-parts with whom they studied. I experienced similar concerns during my own experiences in a graduate physics program at a Canadian university (appendix B). Other West African students have also expressed the de-motivating tone with which they were addressed on issues in their academic pursuits. They describe how their ethnographic backgrounds have been poorly studied, and this influences the way they are treated by both peers and educators. Knowledge about the ethnographic background of others makes it

suitable and helpful in developing the social trends that exist among groups of people. Dzama (1999) speculates on Black students' poor performance in the sciences and offers an alternative explanation about how African educators and learners view such performance. Dzama's concluding remarks that African students have to adopt a mechanistic or pluralistic outlook if they are to do well in science, finds a place in most West African science students' experiences. According to Dzama, fellow African students in other disciplines often are not different in terms of the difficulties experienced by these students in other "developed" nations. For Black students, and in particular West African science students, poor performance in the sciences both in their cultural background and in Canada is not due to changes in their worldviews as a result of their cultural background. "It's partly as a result of the absence of ideal environments, resources and facilities necessary for effective learning of science" (Dzama, 1999, p. 401). The key concepts of the mindset of the 'other' with regards West African Science Students' (WASS) level of knowing/understanding, will highlight the methodology and theoretical framework in my analysis of the standpoints of the effects of the value patterns on students success as both individual and institutional. Often, Black students are found to be on the offensive, arguing about marks that they deserve but are not awarded to them by their lecturer, is viewed stereotypical. This is considered stereotypical. There are two reasons to explain this scenario. First, either the educators do not understand the meaning conveyed in the student's assignment script/essays even if the content of their scripts posit substantial strength and make sense. Secondly, students may have lost marks because they missed some steps in their solution approach (my case in quantitative context in physics). My project organization makes use of the comparative analysis centred on the cultural sensitivity (Hofstede, 1991 & 1997) and the notion of cultural difference (variance) in the transition process of other students lived experiences. Britzman (2003) and Hofstede (1991) discuss the existence of tensions in societal culture and explain that the concept of "cultural sensitivity" should not be seen as a simple trajectory in the transition process.

Britzman (2003) states “one might have an idea, but communicating the idea meaningfully to another individual may become an issue of conflict, knowing that other people come from so many different places with different thoughts and interpretations” (Britzman, 2003, p. 90).

Contrary to Britzman’s idea of gaps in communication, and the existence of tensions based on the mindset of a society with regards how to explain and argue scientifically, I suggest that the academy supports the general social belief that Blacks in general are intellectually incapable of pursuing programs in the pure sciences, hence concluding and confirming the findings by Dzama (1999). Views of Furnham and Bochner (1986), Riley (2005), Apple (2005) and Thompson et al. (1977) were used in the larger global context on issues such as “value-patterns”, “marginalization” and “curriculum.” Some of their reasons were used in deliberating on Hofstede’s work on “culture of knowing” as the centrepiece in this research. Although Hofstede conducted his research findings over a decade ago, it has links to recent research works on the ‘cultural baggage- cultural competence’ themes, which are based on the adaptation of people from particular nation states in a new environment Hofstede (1991 & 1997), Riley (2005) and Zhang (2007).

My working definition of science students includes those with physical science (Chemistry and Physics), engineering, and nursing backgrounds in higher education. Students from West Africa who are in these fields have experienced these transitional issues intensively, both as students and as practitioners. The issues include, but are not limited to shifts in cultural differences and training in science such as: (a) the learner’s preparedness and general anxiety, (b) the learner’s engagement and commitment, and (c) assessment and evaluation. These variables are discussed in the context of selected scholarly literature and interviews. The research explores the learning experiences of four West African immigrant science students who are, or had at one time, studied in major Canadian universities and colleges in Ontario. In West African setting, emphasis is placed on accomplishment including both wealth and academic genius. Anxiety

becomes part and parcel of the ordeal in the experiences of students. The general symptoms of difficulty concentrating, anxiety that is difficult to control, restlessness and repetitive worrying thoughts are all factors that are defined in a person under stress. Some scholars have argued that the problems encountered during the transition process are related to the individual (a ‘deficit position’), whereas other personal acquaintances have argued that it is an institutional problem (personal communication, Bempoh, March 10 & February 8, 2007). Whether the problem is “individual” or “educational” (institutional), I am of the view that such experiences can vary, depending on individual exigencies, idiosyncrasies, or whims.

In this particular research, my argument is about difficulties in the experiences of the West African science students in their academic pursuits in Canadian tertiary educational institutions. These concerns can be traced to the different teaching and learning styles between two “spatially” different education and social settings. The differences in experiences relate that these students are interfacing between two very different higher educational systems. This explanation raises the following questions: *What are some of the experiences of West African science students (WASS) in Canada, and how are these different experiences connected to discourses and discussions that take place in the field of higher education? What are some of the survival skills needed to help these groups of students succeed in the transition process in their academic and social pursuits and overcome the probability of dropping out from the respective programs? Are the problems they encounter individual or institutional or both? What future directions could be put in place to further enhance their chances and interest in pursuing science in Canada? Are there some paradigm shifts that take place in the culture of teaching and learning pedagogies that have affected their capabilities for a sound academic performance? How can they be motivated to yield their full academic potential?*

1.1 BACKGROUND/RATIONALE

My interest in West African immigrant science students' experiences emanates from my own experiences in pursuing graduate studies in physics (1999) in one of the Greater Toronto Area universities. My observations regarding campus life showed that West African science students encounter difficulties in attaining both academic and social stability in Canada. Among the most difficult experiences are the cultural differences (variances) in the pedagogical process of teaching and learning styles in science in the new environment, making new friends, overcoming loneliness, and feeling homesick. Blaut (1987) defines assimilation as a process of smooth transitioning of an immigrant group into the host culture, and I compare his definition to the "acculturation process" as defined by Hofstede (1991). According to Blaut (1987) both terms of "assimilation" and "acculturation" mean the same thing and are interchangeable when applied to the situation of nationalism and decolonisation. When people withdraw from their mainstream old cultures, they encounter numerous challenges and difficulties in addition to the difficulties they experience adapting to a new culture. Conducting this research is important to situate the idea of decolonisation with assimilation and acculturation in my experiences and those of other West African immigrant science students. Acculturation is defined in the *Canadian Oxford Dictionary* as "adapting to or adopting a different culture" (Barber, 1998, p. 9). In this paper, I extend the concept of acculturation to address curriculum in higher education. In higher educational institutions, aspects of acculturation that connect with the different social settings and the new ways of knowing and doing things provide new challenges and difficulties for students throughout the transition period.

This research is important because it is aimed at finding remedies to the various student typologies (classes based on adaptability and type) to which Canadian Higher Education caters, and examines how to inform new students about ways to adjust. These typologies will inform West African international science students about which of the typologies they need to adapt to be successful in their studies and after. My interest, in this research, has prompted me to select

students from the aforementioned science disciplines. It is believed that when these classes of student (typologies) are known, it will further aggregate and explain the particular learner types and the ideal practices to adopt when studying within Canada.

I used to bitterly complain to one of my graduate colleagues about how I felt homesick. Any time Sarah visited and found me playing contemporary Ghanaian music, her advice was that I should play classic Canadian songs instead. She was of the view that to be able go through the transition in experiences swiftly and merge into the Canadian culture I needed to focus on the immediate environment. In West Africa and in particular Ghana, the education system is based on rote learning not experiential learning. To better equip students to learn experientially, Kabba (2005) writes about the need to modify some of the educational practices elsewhere (I make reference to West Africa). To some degree, international students have helped over the years to marginalize themselves from the good cross-cultural social benefits that they are exposed. Marginalization has caused many Sub-Saharan West African science students with a great disadvantage in their transition as a result of conflict between the different educational systems. Hence, there is the need to modify some of the pedagogical practices in Africa in general to equip students to learn experientially (Kabba, 2005). African universities will need radical systematic instruction in the form of inquiry (skill) base learning of science in the classroom (Farmer & Farrell, 1980 & Kabba, 2005). One way of promoting this practice is by focusing on constructing knowledge through active learning.

The emancipation of African students in the Diasporas from the repetitive 'linear model' syndrome as it pertains to teaching and learning is vital. The emancipation theorists call for pedagogical styles, which offer life-long learning (Wink, 2005) in conjunction with what Kabba (2005) describes as hands-on Project-Based-Science-Instruction – PBSI. In my view, the practice debated above regarding hands-on training supports the Freirian concept that says among other things that classrooms ought to become spaces where educators and learners come together to

create democratic dispositions so they can listen to others and show respect for one another even when others views do not match with our (learners) views (Hinchey, 2005). If classrooms/lecture halls are to be seen as places for nurturing cross-cultural diversity, then tolerance and acceptance are two different measurable terms, but also marching pairs that cannot be ignored. Acceptance should serve as the status quo for continuous academic success when classroom ethics and inclusiveness are nurtured in diversity. In the 'Pedagogy of Hope', Freire has this to say in paraphrase: "As educators we are politicians engaged in politics when we educate. And if we dream about democracy, let us fight, day and night, for a school in which the relationship between teachers-students and students-teachers are dialectical. We talk to and with learners so that, hearing them, we can be heard by them as well" (Freire, 2005, p. 121). I am emphasizing the need for educators to make their corrections for students' growth to be flexible to promote motivation rather than demoralization. Some personal acquaintances made mention that often, the comments they receive on their returned assignments make them demoralized. Different value patterns in the cultures from which the professors and students have come, are prime sources of problems that need investigation (Hofstede, 1997).

A critical look at the issue of neglect of hands-on learning in the West African educational system in particular deserves analysis with how students feel about what they know and its relevance (Cherril, 2006). Some of the students that I have spoken with in the past have expressed bitter sentiments regarding what they consider disrespect, periodically feeling looked down upon by either their course mates or from a professorial rank, depending on their idiosyncrasies. Supporting studies reveal similar results for considering the interest of the 'other' in accounts of feeling and respect. Levinas for example states "educational sustainability is possible when the voices of the other are not played down" (cited in Silverstone 2003, p. 475).

Excerpts of informers' experiences and the strategies they used in discussing some of the encounters are described in Chapter four. The discussions and analyses highlight how these

individual's experience are interconnected with literature findings and with my own ethnographic experiences as a minority student and as an educator of science using the social model. Finally, the implications of this study will be directed to discussion with recommendations for future research and implementation.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 OVERVIEW

Questions raised from chapter one are: *what are some of the experiences of West African science students (WASS) in Canada, and how are these different experiences connected to discourses and discussions that take place in the field of higher education? What are some of the survival skills needed to help these groups of students succeed in the transition process in their academic and social pursuits and over the probability of dropping out from the respective programs? Are the problems they encounter individual or institutional or both? What future directions could be put in place to further enhance their chances and interest in pursuing science in Canada? Are there some paradigm shifts that take place in the culture of teaching and learning pedagogies that have affected their capabilities for a sound academic performance and how can they be motivated to yield their full academic potential?*

Studies conclude that many educators carry with them what is termed ‘cultural baggage’ to their new places of academic endeavours (Hofstede, 1991 & 1997 and Riley, 2005). The burden that comes with forfeiting old ways of knowing and doing things is a challenge, which is attributed to many related issues. Hofstede and Riley speculate on such cultural changes and link them to ‘cultural competence’ (Hofstede, 1991 & 1997 and Riley, 2005). Riley, in particular, makes a poignant comment on ‘cultural change’ by arguing that there are times when the cultural beliefs of the receiving nation group could be undoubtedly harmful to learning or excessively discriminatory (Riley, 2005, p. 8). Although Riley puts it in a question form (and not a straightforward attack), some educational institutions in receiving nations can be destructive to the flow and success of newcomers in new educational institution. Culture clashes can be seen in expressions and presentations, as I have witnessed in the fields of mathematics and sciences in

particular. Riley (2005) further states that the changing teaching and learning practices should be viewed as a change of culture rather than as merely a technical matter. He mentions the development of collaborative pedagogy an aspect of multicultural literature, as a panacea for both educators and learners to be able to work successfully in other cultures. I term this suggested practice “nurturing cultural competence.”

I personally experienced the harm that the cultural beliefs of an institution in a receiving nation can cause when I learned of the variation in quantitative presentation in physics assignment solutions. With my British-Ghanaian trained background, I was taught to present clear steps to my quantitative problems, but in Canada and North America in general I was cautioned several times in my problem solving to go straight to point. However, I found that going straight to point and vice versa resulted in accusations; in one such instance, I was wrongfully accused of plagiarizing in one of my assignment. In the aftermath I received an apology letter, but that did not erase the harm already caused by the accusation.

Hofstede begins by saying that inequalities persist in every society and that some people have power more than others (Hofstede, 1997). Hofstede performed a census of the degree of inequalities in society and concluded that employees are afraid to express disagreement with their managers or superiors (Hofstede, 1997). In my observation I find African students at the disadvantage to equity and justice based on cultural inheritance and practice. Hence in my view this offer reasons why most West African students find it difficult to pursue dialogue with their professors in lectures (personal observation). Instead, most West African students are reserved in class. There is a vital need to develop more culturally sensitive approaches that will help to absorb the immigrant West African science students (WASS) into the Canadian educational system. I define culture as the values, the customs, the traditions, and the ways of living that distinguishes one group of people from the other. Culture, according to Hofstede, is patterns of thinking, of feeling, and of acting underpinning the collective programming of the mind, which

distinguishes the members of one group or category of people from another. The key dimensions of societal culture should aim to understand what culture is in terms of education (Hofstede, 1991). This will empower and enable learners, policy-makers, researchers, and practitioners to subsequently develop more culturally sensitive approaches to learning. I agree with Hofstede that “culture is learned, not inherited, and that societal and organizational cultures are qualitatively different concepts” (Hofstede, 1991, p. 5). Emphasis should be placed on how groups of people do things differently from one institution to another and from one geographical setting to another. One’s egotism becomes crucial in the context of how to learn in a new environment. In my former graduate school studies in Toronto, pretending to have no culture was one issue and failing to accept new ways of knowing was another. I feel strongly encouraged to advocate for a blended teaching and learning styles that are necessary and imperative for new immigrant students to adopt and adapt through their experiences. Therefore there is the need for foreign students to adopt and adapt to studying (praxis) in a new institution.

2.1 CULTURAL DIFFERENCES AND CONFLICTS

Britzman (2003), argues that tensions exist between globalization and changes in societal culture. Thus there is the need to continually adopt and adapt to new praxis in a new educational system. She speculates that globalization makes the recognition of societal culture and cross-cultural similarities and differences more, and not less, important. Societal culture is a factor in researching and investigations, which cover the themes curriculum, teaching and learning, leadership, and school-based management. Societal cultures help to facilitate cultural sensitivity when policy, theory and practice are transported between education systems. Cultural dimensions such as group-oriented/self-oriented and limited or holistic relationships are ways of describing, measuring and comparing cultures. Although group or self-orientation has been stated as the core axis around which significant sets of values, beliefs and practices cluster, it is also the

centerpiece, which defines who an individual is. It depends on what cultural context within which one is situated (Britzman, 2003; Dimmock & Walker, 2000). Upon arrival in a new society, one's acculturation is not certainly probable to take the path of a simple trajectory in moving from negative feelings to positive feelings as depicted by the arrow line AX in the figure below. Some of the setbacks encountered in this situation take varying time to overcome with sometimes others enduring longer setback durations than anticipated.

Figure A: 1-Euphoria, 2-Culture Shock, 3-Acculturation, 4-Stable states

The fact that the acculturation stage (level 3) as depicted in figure A, in the transition process is not a simple trajectory is echoed in the work of Furnham & Bochner (1986). Little elaboration and discussions were offered on the possibilities and why international students most often stuck between the acculturation stage as well as the stable stages within their respective transition processes. To some of the new students when the expected guidance and counseling are not offered early, they become victims to the “shortfalls” in the society in which they have come.

2.1.1 EMOTIONAL STRESS IN LEARNING

At stage 4 - C, in figure (A) above, the emotional stability of the international student remains negative in a new milieu compared to the student's origin. This situation has common trends that describe the unexpected experiences of most international students who have little foreign exposure. There are some causes for this effect, many of which are unknown, although for West African science students, the most common cycle is alienation. Most of the students I have communicated with indicate, for instance, that during their laboratory work, they find themselves to be isolated although they want to be part of a group. Another example from my personal experience deals with relationships with both fellow students and educators. Freire (2005), comments that relations are a pivotal element for adaptation, and this theory makes his findings strong in comparison to the related articles. When I entered the graduate school in Canada from my native Ghana, I carried with me hope and enthusiasm. However, the following anecdote describes a typical situation that shattered my dreams. I studied with my fellow Canadian study mates I found in my graduate school program. In one such study group meeting for a Condensed Matter Physics course, we discussed and shared ideas about an assignment. It was quantitative in nature and each one of us presented our individual solutions for marking. The marked scripts were returned without my script. I requested it and I was told later in the professor's office that he believed I had the professors' manual and that I was suspected of copying from this text. The full range of emotions related to this experience compounded the anxiety and frustrations I was facing in having to deal and cope with the new environment. I see disconnectedness a common practice knowingly or unknowingly on the side of dominant group in marginalizing those who needed affection and motivation. Alsop states that education works best when it involves the mind and heart, and that emotions have enormous influence over what takes place in the classroom (Alsop, 2005). Alsop's call for the need to look at emotional work did not involve a discussion of feelings of alienation in the field of science studies. There is a tendency for neglect

in realizing the emotional metaphors and practices embedded in educators' daily language use, irrespective of their importance and how they affect the learner (Zembylas, 2003). I am using Zembylas perspective of the emotional view to look at the issue of alienation in the context of whether immigrant science students will be able to withstand the shock of isolation as something that needs to be discussed. Comparing 4 – B in figure A, the stability of feelings stages on the acculturation curve at 4 – A, it could be said that if the individual is bi-culturally adaptable the better one's transitional success in a new milieu. I believe that the effects of migration on those who have travelled regularly are less as compared to those who migrate for the first time.

2.1.2 VALUE PATTERNS

There is a vast variation in ways in which science students and professors come to share (Riley, 2005) value patterns. The idea of variance and existence makes it difficult for easy acculturation of new students. Value patterns are paramount to issues of cultural experiences and include cultural competence and the transfer of science knowledge. Value patterns engulf aspects of the pedagogical culture, the individual, and the uncertainty risk avoidance, which relate to power distance. I find it worthwhile to further discuss the differences in cultural values between two educational systems of the sending and receiving nations. In this instance, the sending countries include West African nations such as Ghana, Nigeria, Togo and others, and the receiving country is Canada. The value patterns can be analyzed both individually and institutionally with regards to how they enhance or impede progress both academically and socially. Academically, it becomes an individual problem when WASS have to find ways to understand and make meaning from professors' lectures, which are delivered in pedagogically unfamiliar ways, or when educators need to be more familiar with other cultures for effective teaching. It becomes an institutional problem when asking whether the receiving institution

should design bridge courses to help new students to fill in the pedagogical substantive learning gaps if any.

2.2 CULTURAL COMPETENCE

Every new student arrives with his or her portfolio of cultural competence. The cultural competence of the immigrant science student stems from what effects the new environment has on the learning and the adaptation of that individual. Both Hofstede (1991) and Riley (2005, p. 6) speculate on the portfolio of foreign teachers and students as cultural baggage. Further explanation is needed on account of what makes irrelevant the portfolio of foreign students rather than Riley (2005) leaving it vain with scanty and insufficient discussion. From Hofstede's speculation that the term baggage refers to the emotions and experiences that foreign teachers and students carry with them to a new world is not convincing enough and merit argument for cultural critics. Rather what would make it "cultural baggage" and irrelevant is when new students are not able to maximize their acquired knowledge in the new cultural society. This is a vivid account, but opposes the convergence of some social trends that include cultural competence in the modern world (Hofstede, 1991; Langlois et al., 1994). Freire also addresses the needs of both the learner and the teacher in *Letters to Those Who Dare Teach* (Freire, 2005). He explains that the identity of subjects has to do with the fundamental issues of the curriculum they study as well as what is explicitly hidden in what they study. Thus the term 'better off' that is linked to the curriculum foreign students studied modifies the construction of the experiences in the transition process (personal communication, March 15, 2007). The term could be better understood from the perspective of what those claiming to be 'better off' already know and by what means are they categorized. Some foreign students look at other groups as better off when they all have equal opportunities in a new country. The "better off" resonated in a pre-research interview encounter I had with a Ghanaian science student pursuing nursing at a Toronto

university. In his explanation he mentioned that local students find it somewhat intimidating and a challenge to see a foreign student scoring higher marks in courses. The term thus registers as one of the factors that conceptualize personality and identity traits on a particular societal culture of a group of people. The factors of acceptance and tolerance offer avenues for further studies, which include the degree and capability to access facilities by an individual or group of people.

2.3 ACCEPTANCES AND TOLERANCE

The issue of indifference, apart from socio-economic factors, raises panic and fear in the students who travel far and wide to do further studies abroad. When a student's voice is not considered or heard, the individual may feel a strong desire to leave their studies and return home (Ajayi et al., 1996, p. 229-240). In my own experience, the need to go back to Ghana became an issue of contention due to the lack of attention. Daunting practices such as 'who you know' and 'over qualification', among others, cripple the chances of foreign trained personnel who dare to return home freely. Our acquired educational and work experiences, expertise and know-how cannot be utilized fully to the respective nation's advantage. Most of the foreign trained personnel re-enter Ghana with the hope and aspiration of contributing meaningfully to the economic growth of the nation. Their dreams become shattered, and end up becoming national liabilities rather than assets. They cannot find the jobs they seek based on the acclaimed societal slogan 'over qualified.' If foreign trained personnel manage to secure an interview they are told they are 'over qualified' for the position they seek. The reason is that their adequate foreign exposures are a threat to the locally trained people they are competing with for available job vacancies. These elements of marginalizing generate frustrations, resentments and disappointments in these individuals while studying in foreign educational institutions. Subsequently, upon graduation from their respective course programs abroad, or while in school, these students develop a reluctance to return to their home countries. There are two tiers of losers

to the marginalization effect: first, a nation is denied her manpower resources by not receiving back her foreign trained elites. Secondly, an individual or groups of foreign trained experts are denied the chance to put their skills to task to develop a nation in crises. The governments of West African nations want these individuals to return to their homelands after their programs of study, but the basic requirements to sustain their livelihood are not catered for, upon the individuals' return. An avid explanation of marginalization as speculated (Ajayi, 1996) is not an over-generalized contributing factor to West African students' predicament in Canadian Higher Educational institutions. Ghana, along with most African nations, until now has not successfully organized itself to utilize their abundant resources and opportunities to their advantage (Thompson, 1977). Other related forms and ways in which West African students are marginalized include aspects of personality out of the agglomeration (range) of factors, which leads to emotional stress. Value patterns, which incorporate personality influences the sojourner/international student's emotional stress. The definition (Barber, 1998) of a sojourn is a passer-by or one who has a temporary stay in a system or a place. This implies that the individual will return to where s/he hails from after a specific assignment elsewhere. Ghanaian immigrant science students fit into this category. Personality defines the individual's background and upbringing, religion, degree of openness/adaptability, and age. Personality also refers to the individual's country of birth compared to his or her new destination and this inhibits ones chances initially of getting along with the new environment. Personality underscores my interest in finding some of the ways my background could have enhanced my adaptation in Canada in the initial stages. According to many West African acquaintances that I have spoken with in the past the term, indicate that personality helps to moderate cultural values and other ways of knowing (personal communications, Teni, July 20, 2006).

Earlier versions of personality and cultural values had been explained (Giroux, 1997; Morbey, 2006; and Zompatti, 2006). According to these authors it becomes trickier to conclude that there is only one right way. The article by Hinchey on “Finding Freedom in the Classroom” is a good example that sheds light on the other ways of knowing. According to Hinchey (2004), living in someone else’s world of knowing indicates low self-esteem (Maslow, 1943). Hinchey states that Critical Theory is about possibility, hope, and change but I extend the list to include the dimensions of vision and motivation. Without vision and motivation it is impossible to attain success. Culture acts like a mental paralysis (Hofstede, 1991 & 1997); once we are comfortable with our culture it becomes a “mental cage” which blinds the individual from seeing beyond. Cyber localization, according to Morbey (2006), is the provision of alternative strategies in cyberspace. “It provides space for collaborative conceptualization and openness, which should encompass language and engagement” (Morbey, 2006, p.42). This does not pertain to only the cyber world. It also pertains to education since there is a trajectory linking learning and technology as two separate but synchronized educational entities. There are choices to be made and there is no reason why other ways of knowing, including technological ways, could not be made participatory and less expert-driven as emancipation pedagogy (Giroux, 1997) discerns. Both explanations by Giroux (1997) and Morbey (2006) converge on the individual personality and motivational themes. The pedagogy of homogeneity (Zompatti, 2006) permits universities to adopt and adapt common course/common syllabi. Therefore, offering students the opportunity to question everything experientially can be authentic if common science course syllabi are enforced worldwide (Hinchey, 2004; Kabba, 2005; Zompatti, 2006). Hudson (2003) advocates for similar reforms in science education. I though I believe Hudson’s idea of a unified common syllabi demands great work to be done to make the reformation in the higher educational system to become possible.

2.4 CONFLICT WITH TECHNOLOGY

There are some effects and consequences associated with cultural practices and how they have influenced the cultural pedagogies of some international students through the education process. Access and barriers hinge on the cultural value patterns in the application of technology (Hartley & Bendixen, 2001). Every individual and group of people shares their own praxis. In reference to Freire, I define praxis as the development of a theory and practicing the developed theory (Freire, 2006). Praxis should not be a matter of stating beliefs but rather a measure of connecting theory to practice (Britzman, 2003, p. 40). In my case as an example, the incorporation of computer applications in my learning was difficult initially in the Canadian postsecondary educational system. An assignment that could be done in no time by another student could take me ample amount of time due to non-proficiency in the use of technology. I had very little expertise skill in the use of technology in learning just as other foreign students particularly from the developing countries (the trend has changed in the course of time). This is not because all foreign students cannot use technology but because regular technology use was not a daily culture practiced by WASS. It is important for those who travel to Toronto for the purpose of academic work to adopt and adapt bicultural strategies to promote success. There is need for 'blurring boundaries' (Macfadyen & Schonberger 2006). A cross-section of new students would not have rich background experiences with the application of technology in their studies. The effects of the high-tech culture establish common themes on free and open-source technology (Macfadyen & Schonberger 2006; Lessig, 2006; Slevin, 2000). The pressure to shift education into the post-industrial (information) age arises from variety of reasons. These reasons include the promotion of less work, accelerated work, motivation for individuals to work, and sustaining accessibility. These reasons extend the already existing numerous challenges of the higher educational sectors both home and abroad. The present day 'high-tech' media culture performs critical pedagogic

work. It supplements the pedagogic work of both the family and the school, but it is also dominant in all social life. *What are some of the experiences of West African science students (WASS) in Canada, and how are these different experiences connected to discourses and discussions that take place in the field of higher education?* Stated otherwise: *How does the foreign student with very little access to the high-tech tools survive the acculturation experiences in the transition process?* It could be arguable that the challenge of the international student from a developing nation is enormous in this regard. Knowing the limit and restricting oneself within that domain most often eludes those from the less computer/technology driven nations. Everyone has to be accountable to the ‘other’ and it is such accountability, which often cast a spell on the less conversant users of technology (Silverstone, 2003; & Slevin, 2000). Over dependence on the Internet and technology culture hinders the individual’s culture in regards to how we think about the other. The otherness according to Silverstone includes neighbors, visitors, strangers, acquaintances, and new students, in broader sense, which taking into account our individual ways of learning. Technology is viewed as a social force that unifies aside the fact being a tool and also a social process (Stalh, 1999).

2.4.1 TECHNOLOGY AS A SOCIAL PROCESS

One such consideration of technology as a social process that unifies the ‘other’ is the regulation of international trade including education. There are some studies on the need to regulate international trade in education, but there has been little (or no) emphasis made on strengthening the financial portfolio of international students. A profound argument could be made from the point of view of foreign students who find it difficult to receive the supplementary funds proposed to them in their scholarship packages. The study by Apple on “Globalizing Education – Policies, Pedagogies, and Politics” is a good indicator that points to re-examining the financial portfolio of foreign students. Apple discusses the need for universities in ‘developed’

countries to have sustainable policies to help at risk foreign students to succeed. Foreign universities should not aim merely just to attract foreign students (Apple, 2005). In my view, policies should be structured to alleviate foreign students who are facing financial restraints from their faculties to curtail foreign students' dropout rate. Bursary and other related grant agencies should have easy modalities for their acquisition to cater to the acute needs of needy international students. The neglect of foreign students is more pronounced as I have observed, and it is arguable that foreign higher educational institutions are selling themselves as attractive only to claim prestige and fame. Most foreign students I know from West Africa studying in Canada are also the breadwinners of their respective families (Dei, 2004). Extended family pressures thus present another burning issue many immigrant students cannot ignore in their daily role. *Are the problems they encounter individual or institutional or both?* It would be worthwhile to institute a panacea to enable those who are willing to work within and outside campus to be given the chance. Recent promulgated laws in Nova Scotia immigration ease slightly the financial burden and also empowered foreign students who want to work outside campus while in school by applying for work permit (The Toronto Star, 2006). West African Nations are not production countries and thus their citizens find it helpful to immigrate to an industrial country for further studies. In particular, "the old African public system in general did not support and appreciate the enormous potential contributions by higher educational institutions for its industrial growth" (Thompson, 1977, p. 96). The adage that 'when one travels abroad one endeavors to return home with assets' is intercultural, and also observable from one culture to another apart from the West African culture. The mindset of most WASS folks is partly to acquire wealth in the new receiving country and also pursue their academic studies (Thompson, 1977). This is a result of the dependence of other members of the family on their relatives who are pursuing further studies in Canada. The related notions on the speculations above include remitting folklores, kith and kin, and other close relations back home. Other reasons are to enable these classes of students to

purchase all the needed learning accoutrements to support their learning. The support materials include personal computers and other devices apart from the recommended textbooks, in order to facilitate their academic work while in Canada. Financial restraint is one of the many root causes mitigating the difficulty of academic progress of many West African science students (amongst other West African foreign students') studying in North American Higher Educational institutions.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGIES AND STRATEGIES

3.0 OVERVIEW

My experience as a West African international science student in my previous graduate studies in physics, and the challenges that I encountered during my transition period in adapting to the new academic culture, form the basis of my quest to know others' experiences and to investigate pedagogical adaptation skills and typologies that West African science students would need to pursue science in the Canadian higher educational system.

Personal conversations with a number of acquaintances from West Africa studying science in Canada revealed similar experiences for each individual. The acquaintances complained of unfamiliar exposure to new technology, intimidating environments (disconnectedness), unfamiliar pedagogical styles, cultural differences and other challenging experiences, which include the use of sophisticated laboratory equipment and language barriers.

Hofstede (1991 & 1997) and Riley (2005) provide substantial insight into the cultural clashes that arise due to cultural differences in educational settings, but their articles have gaps that offer avenues to argue. I wanted to learn from first hand accounts how West African science students' individually felt in their respective programs and what they want to see altered in the future for new students. I was also interested to learn about the perspective of a science professor with regards to his/her views about the commitment and preparedness of West African students pursuing the sciences in the Canadian higher educational system. The four other participants who are students were interviewed, which include two Ghanaians and two Nigerians. These students were able to participate in this study despite the time constraints.

Interviewing five individuals with varying science backgrounds authenticated the non-idiosyncratic nature of the research. They included pure and applied science graduate and undergraduate students within Toronto who were either graduated or were still in their program of studies.

The analysis of ‘adaptation experiences of individuals’ evolves around questions about differences in the context of one’s background educational system compared to the ‘other’ (Apple et al., 2005; Dei, 2004). This report analysis is situated on the differences between pursuing science in the West African and the Canadian higher educational systems. One of the many goals in conducting the interviews was to elicit moments that did not only illuminate a particular circumstance, but pointed towards growth in an ongoing cumulative inquiry into the trans-local processes (Smith, 2005 & 2006). The trans-local processes include but are not limited to loneliness, pedagogical paradigm shifts, availability of teaching and learning resources and cultural differences. Personal knowledge of these processes led to my interest in advocating for a blended style of teaching and learning. Both emancipation and critical theorist frameworks will be employed to analyze the research findings from both literature reviews and informants. Knowing the views of all the participants, I am interested to see how their experiences connect to themes such as classroom freedom and relationships as discussed by connoisseurs such as Dewey (1944) as cited in (Wink, 2005, p. 130), Freire (1970, 2005 & 2006), and Maslow (1943), and where they differ slightly with Hofstede and Riley’s views. This can be valuable when discussion is centred on analyzing the themes as they resonate to buttress the views of participants from interviews. In this research the entire given names of the participant in all the chapters are pseudonyms.

3.1 TOOLS FOR DATA COLLECTION AND SETTING

My setting for the collected information is the Greater Toronto Area. I preferred the qualitative method instead of quantitative method because the qualitative method is flexible and posit the experiences of individuals. Qualitative analysis was employed because it seeks to find out about the lived experiences of the participants, offers in-depth interviewing, and adds to the richness of the interview. The quantitative approach is more experimental in nature, does not offer a hierarchy of credibility, and does not emphasize the understanding of the perspectives of all participants (Bogdan, 1992 and Bogdan & Biklen, 1998). The qualitative method is straightforward and offers open-ended questions during interviewing and situates the researcher to search for trends and also utilize the opportunities the interview situation presented ethnographically. Ethnography method is about telling our story and not somebody else story, giving an avid description of peoples or cultures. Thurman offers clues that support the suitability of open-ended interview as ideal for this kind of ethnographic research (2003). She explains that analytical papers provide evidence that investigates and evaluates issues in both expository and expressive ways. I chose to conduct semi-structured in-depth interviews with all four participants. In the semi-structured interview I sent pre-selected questions to informants to have general idea of what was expected from them based on their academic and social experiences. Mini audio tape recording device was used in collecting the data. Pre-selecting questions in the semi-structured interview helped in both ways to remain flexible and acted as guides. The use of pre-selected questions was designed to collect information that was used later in the research write-up as data for analysis (Denscombe, 2007). As well, the pre-selection acts as a guide and helps the interviewer to let themes to unfold as the interview travels its full length. These interviews allowed participants to provide vivid accounts from their lived experiences (May, 2001). Such analytical accounts of self are also informative and descriptive just as the findings in this

research. On the other hand, the argumentative nature of the discussions of findings provide evidence to support ones point of view and convince readers that what we write about is right. The direction in this manuscript is partly analytic, expository, and expressive; hence, my interest in choosing the qualitative method. Expository is defined as explaining or giving information regards something/place, whereas expressive writings detail ones' thoughts or emotions and feelings about a situation or event. Analytical writings examine the materials presented critically and purposefully and this offer amongst some of the many reasons why I would be using Critical theory to discuss the findings in this research. The subjects interviewed for this report were students who are studying (or have studied science) in the university and college within the Greater Toronto Area, for physical science degree, environmental engineering diploma and nursing degrees. With the exception of these formal and present students, the fifth participant is a professor currently lecturing in a faculty of nursing, at a large Canadian University.

I interviewed three of the participants in their places of residence at their convenience while the other two were interviewed on a university campus. Each interview lasted between forty-five minutes to an hour. Tommy was interviewed on 27th April 2008 between 3:30 pm and 4:30 pm. The weather was cozy and the atmosphere was serene at the basement of his residence in Ontario. The interview encounter with Skemeh occurred in his apartment in Ontario, on 10th May 2008 between 4:15 pm – 4:45 pm. The condition of the day was bright and cordial and the interview occurred in the participant's sitting room. Vero, on the on the other hand, had her interview on 4th May 2008 between 3:10 pm – 4:10 pm, in the main hall of her apartment. It was a bright sunny Sunday after church and both sides were in good spirit. Teni and Professor May were separately interviewed on a university campus. The dialogue between Teni and me took place in one of the lecture rooms on May 5th 2008 and lasted for nearly an hour commencing from 4:30 pm. It was a sunny and inviting Monday afternoon after my daily school assignment as a high school science

and mathematics teacher. Professor May and I met at her third floor office on the university campus in the nursing building on a nice sunny day after the informant's afternoon lecturing duty (Interview scripts, February 28, 2008). I visited her lecture session to observe how she met the needs of all the diverse learners in her class, emphasizing my interest on equity, openness, acceptability, and inclusiveness. I looked out for some factors that impacted good students – professor interaction in the lecture hall such as ‘give and take’ communication, the lecture hall environment, the resources used and other classroom ethics. All encounters were face-to-face and each participant read and signed informed consent forms before and after the process respectively. The informed consent forms were sent to all participants through their respective email accounts (appendix C). This was to make them feel comfortable and overcome any doubts entertained with regards to authenticity of the safety of what they intended to offer during the interview process. It also gave them ample time to ponder over questions that were troubling their minds before the interview day.

I avoided structuring my questions to enable the theme from individuals to be non-speculative. On the other hand, structuring my questions could have caused differences in meanings to the themes drawn from the informants' experiences. All recorded messages were transcribed verbatim, coded and analyzed.

3.2 PARTICIPANTS' PROFILE

In the table below shows the work related experience of each participant in exception of Professor May whose data was not included. The reason for leaving out work related experience is to use some of her data for analysis to respond to some of the themes from chapter five resonating from the experiences of the principal investigator in chapter five.

Table 3.1: Participants' Related Work Experiences in Canada and elsewhere

Participants	Vero	Teni	Skemeh	Tommy
Work experience related to science	Formally a practicing Registered Nurse in Nigeria. Currently in Canada, working as an industrial worker in Toronto	Formally a practicing Registered Nurse in Nigeria. Currently in Canada and working as a teller at Tim Holton's in Toronto.	Worked as a high school science Chemistry teacher in Ghana. Currently working in Canada as an occasional high school teacher and adult education night school instructor in Brampton.	He declined to speculate on his previous work related experiences while in Ghana. Currently in Canada and working as an engineer in the York Region.

Four West African science students were interviewed for this research. In keeping with balance, equity, and transparency in data and information collected in compiling the research findings, two of the interviewees chosen were of Nigerian descent and two were of Ghanaian descent. The two females are from Nigeria and the males are from Ghana, and all four have science backgrounds. The two females from Nigeria used to be practicing nurses in Nigeria and are currently enrolled in Nursing Program at a large University in Canada. The two males from Ghana are past graduates from their science programs and are working in Toronto. One of the males was a science teacher in Ghana and currently works with a public School Board as a science teacher with the Adult and Continuing Education Department. He holds a doctorate degree in chemistry from a prestigious North American University. The other male is an engineer, working with the York Region Environmental Engineering Department, who studied environmental engineering. He holds a diploma in environmental engineering from a college in Ontario. Irrespective of the background of these participants my information still contains gaps, because the data does not reflect the entire population of West Africans in the Diaspora. Secondly the data collected reflect

only a cross section of science students from few African countries (Ghana & Nigeria), neglecting Togo, Senegal, Burkina Faso, Cote d'voire Liberia and others.

Professor May has an extensive background based on the countries visited in the past in her nursing/teaching career practicing as a nurse, a community dweller, and an educator. Although she has the first set of Black students of West African descent, she has worked extensively with Black students in her teaching career. The female West African interviewees, Vero and Teni, are undergraduate acquaintances and my schoolmates. I met them when I visited Professor May during one of her preceding lecture periods for a scheduled interview in February 2008. My visit to Professor May's class was intended help me familiarize myself with her teaching styles and observe her comportment in her teaching session, which involved a cross-cultural set of students from different Nation States, globally.

The informative discussions on self-esteem according to Hinchey (2004), offer an avenue to explore the paradigm specifics in this research. First, I will compare the commensurability in teaching and learning between two higher educational systems using course outlines and information supplies. In my West African experiences, the institutions offer the program outlines to students. In my tertiary education in West Africa, I rarely received a course outline indicating the breakdowns of what was to be covered, and how marks would be awarded. But the course content of both the Canadian and West African Science courses are basically the same (appendix B). Secondly, in Canada, there are hosts of websites, which offer a deeper understanding in academic work. In my own experience, textbooks and lecture notes have been the main sources of information in pursuing physics and other courses. In Canada, the opposite is witnessed, partially due to the versatility of Internet resources. Thirdly, I will compare the similarities and difference in the culture of practice. The West African style of science training is more theoretical and more experiential in Canada. I am aware that other factors exist that tote up the

general experiences of West African students, but my focus is primarily on the paradigm specifics stated above. I also understand that different teaching and learning styles and stated that style permeates all aspects of life. *What are some possible criteria solutions to these issues?* Critical radical pedagogues view of thinking deeper into situations, York University's motto of seeking diversity in education, as well as the emancipation theorist argument for questioning everything all help to find solutions to the dilemmas faced by West African science students (Callender, 1997; Hinchey, 2005; Kabba, 2005).

Vero and Teni (cohort students) are anxiously looking forward to graduating and getting into the Canadian work force with great expectations. They both lamented their work experience whilst in Nigeria and describe the variations they see in some of the nursing practices here in Canada. Vero works in the industrial sector at the moment in order to be able to manage her family. She particularly spoke at length about how different she sees the hospital delivery (maternity) system here in Canada, what amuses her, and what she's seen learnt in Canadian system. Vero also detailed how some terms were new to her such as 'code blue' in the Canadian setting. She said it took her some time to understand code blue to mean a patient in critical period which could lead to death and how as a nurse, one would have to respond in such emergency times when on ward duty in the hospital. Periods such as the code blue demands more readiness and exhibits of one's leadership qualities. Vero mentioned how some of her classmates pull the race cards in terms of studying with her and other West African students in the nursing program. According to Vero, the professors she has encountered are helpful but a few did not have strong control over the course they taught. She particularly spoke about one of her professors who had poor classroom management skills, which affected his class control. The professor did not know how to ensure he was in the leadership control seat to facilitate students' contributions. Referring to *Table 3.2* below, I am of the notion that unlearning and relearning do not matter how much

knowledge an individual had gained in the past and this affirms the notion of continuous lifelong learning (Wink, 2005). Vero posit that although she had so much nursing experience, she was open to learning new information in the Canadian nursing industry; hence, her enrolment in the nursing program at the university. As reflected on the table below, all of the participants' backgrounds indicate each participant's extensive number of years of schooling and practice. Unfortunately, this experience was not sufficient to fetch them their dream occupations upon migrating to Canada.

3.3 DESCRIPTION OF PARTICIPANTS

Table 3.2 - Characteristics of interviewed participants.

Name	Gender	Work Experience	Area of study/Work
		Canadian and other	
Tommy	Male	15 years, < 10 years	Chemistry, Environmental Engineering
Vero	Female	2 years, > 10 years	General science, Nursing student
Skemeh	Male	3 years, < 10 years	Chemistry, Adult Science Teacher
Teni	Female	2 years, > 10 years	General science, Nursing student
Professor May	Female	Over 15 years	Nursing Professor

According to Teni, some professors should accept other cultures and they should be prepared to try to learn from other cultures as a way of motivating foreign students. She also speculates that some professors should check their nuances and biases for a free and equitable classroom practices such as awarding of marks and accepting contributions from both locally trained and

internationally trained students as all-important. In her view, class and race still form a strong stigma on the part of some educators with regards to Black students' academic experiences. She has been struggling with this dilemma for a long time.

Tommy discussed how tough it was learning science for the first time in Canada in his Environmental Engineering program. He had very little science background from Ghana, where he had his primary and secondary education, which by then had the 7 – 5 – 2 system - seven years primary which include kindergarten, five years secondary and two years pre-university preparation education. He lamented on how he struggled through his science courses, particularly chemistry, and ended up trailing some of his courses at college. Nonetheless, he persisted and took courage and made it through the turbulent times. He also speculated on how he had to struggle to support himself and his nuclear family of a wife and two children. Tommy did not shy away from saying that although the British colonized his native Ghana and as such English was medium of education and administration, he experienced language, e problems in the way he presented his assignments and in the way he communicated with his teachers and fellow North American born and raised students on campus.

Skemeh's experience storyline was similar to the experiences of the others. He purposefully migrated to North America to pursue his graduate studies in Aquaculture (the study of water ecosystems) and not by migration to seek greener pastures. He said:

Though it is the same science but the emphasis in West Africa is totally different from the emphasis in North America with respect to Canada. Therefore when one migrate to study in North America, since there is a shift in emphasis, one has to devote much time to find out which area he/she is deficient and make up for it. For instance find out the pre-requisites of all the courses you are registered to take and meet them before registering. One have to study vehemently since it is a different ballgame altogether. Since one is coming in new with all the challenges, it is advice that whenever you are given a project work start work on it as early as possible forestall delay which will course you to rush to submit your assignment with poor proof reading – (Interview script, May 10, 2008).

He emphasized the students' commitment and knowing which students' typologies are best suitable to succeed in the Canadian setting. He mentioned his experience studying and teaching science in Ghana, West Africa before migrating to North America for higher education. He emphasized that in West Africa whenever students are given a problem to solve quantitatively, they show every logical calculation step that one took to arrive at the final answer. If the student arrives at a wrong answer, the teacher can look at the student's logical steps and award partial credit. This philosophy is what has guided Skemeh this far in his education. He drew a contrast between the North American and the West African educational systems: He further explained that he had studied and taught science here, but because most of the kids have sophisticated calculators and that entire staff, they key in all the figures into the calculator and they end up writing the last two steps and that is it. That is one of the big difference I see in problem solving based on sophisticated calculators. *How wrong is a professor when the assignment scripts of an International student are handled differently?* Qualitatively, such as in essay writing, Skemeh said in West Africa, when students asked to write any type of essay, they were taught to start with the introduction, then the objective and main body and conclusion. In North America, the processes are very similar except that most of the time students do not take the time to write the introduction. Rather, they go straight to the point and sometimes too they list the factors, for instance, and state just one sentence about the topic. But in the West Africa setting, students are taught to list the factors with regards to a topic, explain, and give examples (expanded form).

In an interview with Professor May, she posits that trust and confidence in her students without limitations to any of them irrespective of their background of origin is her norm in practice. She sees all the students, including the West African science students in her class, presently and in the past succeeding just as the local Canadian students. She particularly speculated on the strong spirit, readiness and resilience that the West African students bring to her class. I personally witnessed these qualities in her participatory teaching style during my

observations. Professor May has travelled to other parts of the world and that makes her open to accepting other cultures and ways of doing things in her class with ease.

3.4 INTERVIEW QUESTIONS AND DESIGNED PROCESS

My mode for interviewing constituted a semi-structured approach with pre-constructed guiding questions. The reason for this was to have absolute authority over the kinds of questions I would ask my participants regarding their experiences, but not necessarily the ultimate questions. I left the questions open since I did not know what the various informants' experiences were as in session 3.4.1 and (appendix A).

The format of the interview was made flexible and the questions were constructed with simple language. I made the questions open-ended in order to engage the participants in a discussion format rather than in strict confinement (Robin, 1993; Bogdan & Biklen, 1993).

3.4.1 INTERVIEW GUIDED QUESTIONS

The designed questions to guide the interview were spread in the following pattern: to create a rapport for relaxing discussion and to seek participants' background information, their pedagogical paradigm shift and their interest in the way they want future science student to be treated and directed.

A). Participants background information

- i. *Can you tell me about your experience in learning science in West Africa?*
- ii. *Can you tell me about your experiences in learning science in North America specifically the type of program you studied and what are some of the pertinent experiences?*

B). Pedagogical paradigm shifts

- iii. *Did you notice any difference in problem solving and what are these? How do the problem solving between the two educational systems vary quantitatively (mathematical way), and in the qualitative (essay writing)?*
- iv. *Can you elaborate on some of the challenges you encountered in North America and how did you overcome them?*

C). Future interest

- v. *In your capacity as graduate and in your capacity as a community dweller, what advice would you give to West African Canadian science students and others who have immigrated here to do science?*
- vi. *What advice if any would you give to the professors' who handle us herein North America in the sciences? Looking at cultural differences?*

CHAPTER FOUR

FINDINGS

4.0 OVERVIEW

After carefully scanning through all the information collected, I am able to structure interviewees' responses into individual categories. In tabular form, individual informants' responses are characterized into themes namely: resources and hands-on experience of learners; marginalized and disconnected (aspects of emotion with regards to technology, environment and segregation); committed educators and learners; educators' and learners' cultural differences (cultural variance, cultural competence, cultural baggage, and individual differences); and cultural capital and a voice in accountability (language barrier). The themes were deduced from the data collected from participants as each posited their respective science-related learning and work experience both locally and abroad (*Table 3.1, chapter 3*). In as much as there were some similarities in the discrete categories, it is worthwhile to note that the views and experiences shared by each of the participants were quite different. I reference Hofstede (1991, p. 210), and particularly the cultural shock and acculturation stage in the acculturation process (Furnham & Bochner, 1986), in the analysis of feelings (emotions) that individuals go through during and after their periods as science students in both Canada and in West Africa (figure A, chapter 5). While some of the feelings are intended I am interested in discussing the unintended because they connect with individual's experiences.

The 'unintended conflicts' connect the 'affect domains', which include: feelings, values, self-efficacy, self-doubting, and self-confidence. Campbell (1986) described 'unintended conflicts' as those that "often arise during intercultural encounters and which happen although nobody wants them and often brings suffering on the people involved" (cited in Hofstede, 1991, p. 208). There are several psychological and social strands that are associated with intercultural encounters in

the life of the foreigner, sojourner, immigrant, and new student. Most common of these strands, with regards the foreigner is his/her feelings towards the new cultural environment. These are extracts of the quotes that enlist some of the descriptors that resonated from the informants' stories during the interviews.

The commitment to one's urgent needs to succeed as a student in one's respective science program resonated among all the participants' experiences. Some of the themes are common in the way they were employed, whereas others were distinct with respect to the participants. Those that seem similar will be grouped and the non-similar ones will be presented separately.

4.1 TOMMY

Tommy has worked as an environmental engineer with one of the town councils for over fifteen years. He would not reveal the type of jobs he did when in West Africa, although it appears he was in high school. He explained he found friends (both schoolmates and members of his local community) to be very influential helping him assimilate to the Canadian culture and also for developing specific learning skills. On this topic, he stated that working with course mates serves as one of the best options for re-enforcing language and learning skills. He stated:

At least I tried not to do things alone because at times it was very difficult and as I said I do speak English but here you are in a class with other thirty to forty students and the lecturer does not have time to waste time on you. There are so many things he/she may run over which you may not understand and then even though I speak English but whatever is said you have to take it your mind translate it into your language and then re-translate it into English. Whether that was true or not that is the way it works. With the translation process, it may take sometime and before you know the teacher had already gone and so you have to create a 'buddy-system' that you can go to whenever there is something that you don't understand. Such 'buddy-system' could be a person or a group to solicit for understanding as a committed active learner – (Interview script, April 27, 2008).

Farmer and Farrell assert how teachers unintentionally affect students' attitudes by their verbal and nonverbal behaviour. They argue it is not easy for teachers to identify how they unintentionally ignore real-life applications in their assignments and test as well as in their

instructions without systematic feedback from students (Farmer & Farrell, 1980, p. 230). Without feedback from students, teachers cannot make adjustments to meet the needs of the students who cannot gain a full understanding of the science topic being addressed. Turning to fellow students for re-enforcement, as Tommy described, becomes the best option for knowing and understanding. Although Farmer and Farrell made their reference with regard to high school students, this practice of neglect by educators in meeting students' needs also applies in higher education cycles. Within the framework of sharing resources, as in Tommy's example, fellow students became the resource personnel for other students. Morbey's assertion of collaborative conceptualization and openness, which encompass language and engagement, gives Tommy's view a positive note as recalled from Chapter two (Morbey, 2006, p.42).

Tommy further explained how his financial position was not making it easy for him to pursue his education in Canada. He described how he lived on student loans and how, on weekends, he would go and deliver pizza just to support his wife, and two kids. It was very difficult and a challenge, but said he could not say because of lack of money school was out. A lack of education would mean staying wherever you are for the entirety of your life. He further explained that when he realized that he could not spend the rest of his life in Canada doing odd jobs, he put himself together and upgraded his education. These are his words:

I stopped whatever job I was doing and whatever money I was getting just to go to school and all that I relied on was my student's loan as I said, and so I had to find a way to survive. Through all these times it wasn't easy. You are bound to face so many challenges and you have to make up your mind that you are here for something and these challenges will not be there forever and look ahead and move on – (Interview script, April 27, 2008).

He lamented on the need to overcome language difficulties, although he hails from Ghana, South of the Saharan West Africa, where the British once colonized. English is the medium of expression and the official language of administration and educational instruction. Tommy had this to say: "You have to be able to get over with language issues first."

Tommy stressed the need to be a receptive learner and do as the professors want you to do in order to be successful in one's program while studying in Canada. He had this to say about his Geology instructor's remarks:

You are here to learn and pass your course so you just only have to work towards your marks and when you leave school you can use your religious ideas but not in the classroom. If you have some issues about the way things are done and are not suitable to you do not make a comparison but learn and later go to the instructor about what you think about a particular topic - (Interview script, April 27, 2008).

Such infusions into the equation of learning through questioning generate lack of self-confidence in learners. Tommy's instructor's advice defeats what educators for classroom democracy, such as Freire, Giroux, Hinchey and Dewey, advocate. When hegemony is operating, the less powerful do as they are told and accept the inferior roles and instructions offered them without question. Referenced from Chapter two, Hinchey is of the view that to have an authentic understanding of what students learn learners must have the freedom and right to question everything (Hinchey, 2004, p. 20). According to her explanation, without critical questioning, learners are continually being driven by someone else's culture and ideas. This connotes the testimonial Freire calls the "banking system of disseminating information in educators, which is against the constant commitment to equity and justice" (Freire, 2005, p. 32 & 100; Wink, 2005, p. 32). Learners owe their praxis to practicing what is theorized and not just accepting is stated as beliefs, which intend breeds' oppression. "Teaching and learning is dialectical to fully live the context of practice and theory" - (Freire, 2005, p. 142). Although Tommy has good point, the struggle for humanization, for the emancipation, for empowering and overcoming alienation, for the affirmation of all persons would be meaningless with such critical disengagement of the student's views (Freire, 2006).

4.2 VERO

Vero had been a practicing Registered Nurse while in Nigeria, which is another formal British Colony. Now living in Canada, she enrolled in the newly structured nursing program at a university in Canada. She experienced the disappointment of not getting her dream job when she migrated to Canada with her family (comprised of her husband, two sons and a daughter), and had to work in part-time jobs to keep up her family. Vero points out that she enrolled in the accelerated nursing program because she believes she knows what it takes to bounce back. She narrates it this way:

Though we say we do not have the facilities back home, we find out that we can do the research on our own because we have sayings that ‘do it your-self.’ You really want to know and you will find the lecturers/teachers in the schools in West Africa really struggle to impact the message to you. It’s not like they were ‘spoon-feeding’ us. They really perform to ensure that we as learners understand – (Interview script, May 4, 2008).

Vero’s rationale for helping other West African science students in the future is to be fully prepared to meet the challenges that are awaiting them as they strike out to pursue higher education in North America, and in particular Canada. In a statement that seems to support what Hofstede (1991) and Riley (2005) explain as cultural baggage, Vero coined it in the phrase: ‘It is not all a bed of roses.’ They should get ready and be prepared for what they are coming to meet here. Do not just come and feel that everything will go smoothly and that money will come in no matter what your qualifications and education are from back home. For those that are here, she advises that they should put in more effort. They should not say they have one degree so that’s fine. They should make the best use of opportunities that they are given while they are here so that some day they can impact the skills and knowledge gained to others both folks within the Diaspora and in West Africa. She contradicted her statement of forgetting what one carries with them into a new milieu as mentioned earlier but instead argued in support of learners lived experiences. For example, she made mention of how one of her favorite professors on campus asked for definitive answers from his students in the lecture theatre. This expectation made all of

his students feel important in class. Vero said that the professor asked questions as: *How is it done in your background or in your culture?* And this was to enable her professor to obtain first-hand information from his students. This was seen as a sign of the professor's respect and commitment to his students. Interestingly, this refutes Hofstede and Riley's assertion that dropping one's cultural baggage and accepting the new system is the best method for assimilation and learning (Hofstede, 1991 & Riley, 2005).

4.3 SKEMEH

Though one may argue that is common among most students, Skemeh, who is an Adult Education teacher, and presently teaching with a public School Board, relates his commitment to what the individual thinks is good and ideal. He asserts:

When I was in North America and realize so many things had to be done on the computer, it was a enormous challenge. There were many of the software's I have never heard of their names but because I had to use them, I spent extra time to learn them and which, eventually helped me. That which helped me was taking extra time to learn the things that I did not know but were helpful in building the bridges aimed at achieving success – (Interview script, May 10, 2008).

Skemeh recalled how he decided to mend strengths and weaknesses in the courses that he needed but did take while he was a student in Ghana, West Africa. He remarked:

Since there is a shift on practice, and emphasized, one has to devote much time to find out which area he/she is deficient and make up for it. For instance find out and meet the requirements of all the pre-requisites of the courses you are registered in to take before registering – (Interview script, May 10, 2008).

This resonates in what Vygotsky captioned in the phrase: "In the process of teaching and learning I encounter new ways and ideas" (cited in Wink, 2005, p. 30). One has to study continuously since it is a different ballgame altogether and one has to reach back to move forward as an informed learner.

4.4 TENI

Teni was a practicing nurse in Nigeria and is enrolled in the Nursing Program a larger university. She immigrated to Canada barely three years ago. Currently she works as a cashier in a Tim Horton's coffee store. She has it this way in her Canadian experience: "Here in Canada, the professors are very thoughtful. They have created after school hours meant for students so that if they have issues/problems they can approach them for one-on-one discussions where they are able to solve some issues and they also encourage students to do group studies" – (Interview script, May 5, 2008).

Teni's advice for people who might follow suit in the future or those who are already in the educational system is that they should put their emotions behind and face the tasks ahead of them. She is of the notion that if these qualms of emotions persist, then chances of succeeding are limited. She analyzed it like this:

They should not feel shy at all when they are out there and they become handicapped with the application and use of technology such as the computers, document camera, and overhead projectors to mention a few. Rather they should speak up and ask for help. They should use the peer-body system to seek extra help (Interview script, May 5, 2008).

This is similar to what one of the participants, Tommy expressed as "body-system."

Reflecting on myself as an immigrant minority, the shared experiences above are similar to my own experiences both in the past and present. I have found that most foreign science students, particularly those from West Africa need to understand the typologies that the Canadian higher educational institutions cater to, and the need to make adequate preparation to meet these standards. Some of the things we face, as science students, prove painstaking when they act as obstacles to our progress. Overcoming the fear of operating new technology for the first time and the fear of loneliness, as well as acquiring new knowledge are typical and common examples in my case as a new student to Canada. Supporting studies reveal similar results and posit that if those things that cause fear do exist, we must match them against the available possibilities of

overcoming and becoming successful. As Freire cautions, what individuals must not do is to stop at the instinct level of our emotions, feelings, and intuitions (Freire, 2005).

4.5 PROFESSOR MAY

During her interview, Professor May shared some of the difficulties new students experience, such as: Not knowing what you going to be wearing next month you know because the temperatures are changing and it is getting hotter and I thought how much hotter or colder is it going to be. Skemeh shared similar views. Professor May further elaborated how the environment could be a shocking experience to new students, especially to West African science students, in her words:

One thing about this nurses some of them have come directly but we are not recruiting, so a number of them have been here working. Some of them have been working in coffee shops, convenient stores, Zellers, as Personal support workers (PSW's) in various jobs you know very underneath their credentials. Some of them have been here ten to fifteen years so some of the acclimatization of the city environment they are familiar with. Those that have come directly, quiet few of them have come from Saudi Arabia, the Philippians it was a little bit harder, not because of the buildings, temperature and seasonal changes here in Canada (Interview script, February 28, 2008).

New students are bound to face varying acculturation difficulties as depicted in the acculturation curve in Chapter five. Curves TA, TB, TC explain the effect based on the environment, social and economic factors in the adaptation process (Hofstede, 1991).

Another way of adapting to a system is reading through the lines of how people willingly acknowledge others based on the rich diverse knowledge they bring to class and the Country. The “banking model in teaching lacks the respect that learners need from educators and does not categorize both educators and learners as informed learners” (Hinchey, 2004, p. 43 & Wink, 2005, p. 153). Professor May recounts it as the following:

Well as you saw today I used adult learning principles and acknowledged the fact that the students' I have are bringing a wealth of knowledge and experience to the classroom. I think that my respecting and acknowledging them are extremely important in building

self-esteem to my students who come from another country – (Interview script, February 28, 2008).

According to Freire, the ‘banking’ concept of education is a form of oppression. He argues that the problem-posing concept of education, which is about liberation and acceptance, is most suitable. Freire speculates that: “Teachers talk about what reality is as though it is motionless and predictable. Teachers expound on a topic completely alien to the existential experience of the students. Content, is detached from what reality to give content significance” (Freire, 2006, p. 71). In Professor May’s statement, she recounts that all knowledge is important and that no knowledge is baggage and supports it as cultural competence. She said: “When you talk about the cultural competence as the knowledge of others, which, they carry, into a new milieu (a new society) or into a new learning environment, then cultural baggage does not apply” – (Interview script, February 28, 2008). On the other hand, failure to use these competences to harness (galvanize) their future then makes the ‘carry-over knowledge’ a baggage, as Hofstede (1991) and Riley (2005) argue, which I disagreed with earlier. It is the perception of what both educators and learners have for one another most adds to this culture of practice of viewing some knowledge as good and others as bad based on geographical background. The question that needs to be answered to this effect is: *Are there some paradigm shifts that take place in the culture of teaching and learning pedagogies that have affected their capabilities for a sound academic performance and how can they be motivated to yield their full academic potential? In what ways should teachers have to teach (science curriculum) in the Canadian context to cater to the different background needs of all students in the post-secondary educational system?* She was of the view that teaching should be done in a way that will bring and maximize a learner’s understanding, from what learners are bringing into the lecture rooms, what their experiences have been, and their knowledge level. When teaching is focused on a level that learners can move into fairly quickly helps in their self-confidence. Teaching should not be something that is way

beyond learners' abilities to grasp and enjoy. However, Professor May, cautioned that if such lessons are below their level and expectations they get bored and not interested in listening to it. It is vital that educators understand learners to create a solid start point in the education process.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

5.0 OVERVIEW

During my observational visit to Professor May's class in late February 2008, I noticed that close to eighteen percent of the students were women of West African descent. I asked if there were any peculiar traits that make these students different from the rest of the students. She said the West African students have strong resilience and self-determination. She speculated seeing them succeed in the same way as the students of other nationalities and she see's them on equal levels to success as students from the Asia, Europe, the Latin America and those who are Canadian born (May, February 28, 2008). I asked the question, based on the assumption, of the broad spectrum of factors ranging from economic, historic and cultural factors that affect school learning and performances (Ogbu, 2008). Ogbu's finding confirms Freirian's point on the need for recognition of the existence of cultural inheritances, which should result in respect for educators and learners on the other hand (Freire, 2005). These cultural differences form the main argument on why people from different demographic regions struggle to fit into a new culture. For instance education in North America is Euro-centric whereas education in Africa is more Afro-centric and thus a difference in approach in reasoning, and doing things. In my physics graduate studies in Canada I was on scholarship and was haunted by the fear of not making the grade owing to my new environment. This was not the case in the experiences of the students I met in Professor May's lecture. These students had been in Canada for some years and were employed in coffee shops, grocery shops, Zellers, and other retail and merchandise stores in the GTA, as well as others working as personal support workers (PSW). They have had a progressive transition in their programs partly because most of them are in the later stages of adaptation depicted as TA, in the acculturation curve (figure B). This class of students, described by curve TA, are acclimatized and familiar with the city environment. Previous conversations with

numerous Ghanaian science students in Canada revealed loneliness to be a common feeling among international students. In one such conversation with Bampoh, a Ghanaian nursing student in a larger university in Ontario, he mentioned loneliness as key retarding factor (personal communication, March 10, 2007). Many other Nigerian and Ghanaian students I have talked with also described their situation as having few or no friends in the new country. They attributed their loneliness to the fact that their time was restricted owing to the heavy academic workload, combined with re-studying of English as second language in the Canadian style.

In my experience in the classroom, both as an educator and learner, I have observed that alienation often results due to misunderstandings between educators and learners. This alienation could reflect, “How ill prepared the educational system in Canada is to cater to the diverse cultural learning needs of some learners based on their background of origin” (James, 2005, p. 3). This may be the result in a lack of adequate background knowledge on the part of the educators, although this is not a measure of the cultural competence on the side of either the educators or learners. When interviewed, Professor May reiterated she encourages her class to listen to one another’s voices and emphasized that educational sustainability is possible if the voices of the ‘other’ are audibly heard and not played down (Silverstone, 2003). The themes that resonate in the participants’ views are: resources and hands-on experience of learners; marginalized and disconnected; committed educators and learners; educators’ and learners’ cultural differences, and cultural capital and a voice in accountability.

Skemeh revealed that hands-on training is crucial for self-efficacy and recommended that professors who supervise/teach West African (research) science students should offer these students more hands-on laboratory work to cushion them for future experiential scientific research. Alsop defines “self-efficacy as being different from self-esteem and explains that while self-efficacy emphasizes resources and confidence, the later emphasizes the socio-cognitive judgments of an individual’s capabilities” (Alsop, 2005, p. 84 & Kabba, 2005, p. 3). Although

both Alsop and Kabba specifically dwell on grades 7 – 12 students, their findings are also applicable to students at higher education levels. In the West African context, according to Skemeh's speculation, although science students believe that they have the confidence to do their science laboratory tasks they do not use the available resources.

Another factor for discussion is small class size. The small class size allows for an individual's attention and collaboration with peers. Such practice for self-efficacy is prevalent in the Canadian style of teaching and learning but not catch up to the West African educational system and it's due to poor finance and policies. Different ways of knowing in another society can critically be examined based on individuals' own self-knowledge and self-efficacy (Wiggins & McTighe, 2001). According to Hofstede (1991), the key dimension of societal culture is to understand the meaning of culture in terms of education. This process empowers and enables learners, policy-makers, researchers, and practitioners to subsequently develop more culturally sensitive approaches to learning (Apple, 2005). I contend that institutions and policymakers need to define their policies in measurable terms so that cross-cultural comparisons can be accurately and validly made to the advantage of both the local and international students. Jegede (1991) concludes with two postulates with the resonating term of commitment as emanated from the interviews with Skemeh and Tommy. The first calls for restructuring science education in Africa and redeveloping its teacher education programs to be philosophically rooted in and guided by its own imperatives. The second suggests the integration of traditional culture with western science and mathematics (Jegede, 1997). Other recommendations are using the central ethos of the African traditional society, which includes 'solidarity and oneness.' Though I find relevance in the postulates as they help to sustain the community and education, Jegede's views are partially close to Hofstede's concern for integration of cross-cultures in postsecondary institutions. The neglect of the needs of other foreign learners nurtures tension in the educational system as posited by Britzman (2003).

Another analysis drawn from the findings is availability of interdisciplinary courses. Canadian universities offer a wide range of opportunities for academic inquiry. These course profiles as well as engagement with contemporary practice of teaching, learning and curriculum design handicaps the West African science students. This and other factors, such as non-effective teaching profiles, have contributed to the abstract science pattern in learning science within the African context when compared to learning science in the New Zealand education (Bishop, Berryman, Cavanagh, & Teddy, 2007). This explains why many international science students from West Africa often takes longer periods to overcome the gaps as depicted in figure B below, in stages 2 and 3, the cultural shock stage and acculturation stage respectively. One way or another, the foreigner experiences a form of cultural shock, based on their basic values (Hofstede, 1991, p. 209).

Figure B: 1-Euphoria, 2-Culture Shock, 3-Acculturation, 4-Stable state Hofstede, G. H (1991, p.

The Euphoria state is the honeymoon and the excited state of traveling to new places and seeing new landmarks for the first time. The cultural shock state is the period when real life starts in the new destination (world) and adjustment becomes imperative to implement. The Acculturation state is when the new student learns to function and perform under the new per-supposed conditions. The Stable state is the period of taking things easy as an immigrant, new resident, or new student in a new environment.

5.1 COMMITTED EDUCATORS AND LEARNERS

In Chapter four, Tommy described on how he lived on a meagre student loan and how on the weekend he would go and deliver pizza just to support his wife, and two children. He said it was very difficult and a challenge but he could not say because of lack of money school was out of his life. In his words: “That would mean staying wherever you are for the rest of your life, so you have to overcome them” (Interview script, April 27, 2008). Tommy is committed, informed and active learner. Challenges are part of life and success often comes with some failure. Dewey says learners must be given the opportunity to fail in their practices so that they can relearn. Dewey’s pragmatic expression is more directed to teachers rather than the learner (cited in Wink, 2005, p. 107). Tommy, with regard to relearning, believed that it takes time to relearn and that is the reason why, as a learner in a new environment, one has to create a ‘buddy-system’ so that there is someone to go to whenever there is something that needs further explanation. The ‘buddy-system’ could be a person or a group that can be solicited for help.

As an informed learner, Vero emphasized that in her program of studies currently, she is committed and knows what it takes to research for information. She did not fail to draw on the gap that exists between the two different educational systems in terms of the availability of equipment. She believed in the principle of “do it your-self.” She also gave praise to the committed lecturers/teachers in the schools in West Africa with regards to how they struggle to

impact their students' education: "Its not like they were 'spoon-feeding' us. They really do things to ensure that we understand as learners" (Interview script, May 4, 2008).

On the topic of commitment in commensurability, Skemeh viewed it from his own experience when he was in North America during the initial stages of his graduate school program. Skemeh described the abundance of computer application software, which he had not seen nor used it before. He said: "I spent extra time to learn them and which, eventually helped me in achieving success" (Interview script, May 10, 2008). One of the visible traits observed in Professor May's class when I visited late February 2008 was "acceptance" among members of her class. Everyone had the dispensation to question, criticize, and debate freely, which in the end helps students to achieve success confirming Skemeh discussion of making the extra effort (Interview script, February 28, 2008). He committed and devoted much time to find out which areas he was lacking in and made up for these gaps. I had a similar experience in my graduate physics program where I was lacking modern optics as a pre-requisite to pursue non-linear optics. I did not find out the courses I had to register to meet the requirements and expectations for the higher courses before registering my main courses. Skemeh puts it as a different 'ball-game' (expect the unexpected) altogether and one must study vehemently to overcome the gaps in the educational process.

The stakes are high in achieving academically and caring for one another is a communal practice. In Teni's views, based on her experience, Canadian professors are thoughtful with the creation of after school hours meant for students to further engage on a one-on-one basis for tutorials. A committed educator is one who is ready to open up to his/her students to understand their situations. Paulo Freire highlights such commitment as a virtue that is often accompanied by other virtues such as humility (comprising self-respect and self-confidence), lovingness and tolerance (Freire, 2005). Dewey and Vygotsky believe that "if learning is not meaningful to learners it is irrelevant what the instructor does" (cited in Wink, 2005, p. 75). Teaching and learning are filled with emotions and Teni advocates that fellow West African science students in

the Canadian Higher Educational system should put emotions behind and face the realities. She is of the view that if these emotional uncertainties persist, then the chances of succeeding are limited. She concludes such ideas in the words: “There should not be shyness at all when handicapped with the application and usage of technology such as the computers but rather speak up and look for the remedy” (Interview script, May 5, 2008). Some ways of overcoming such difficulties in Tommy’s view is to form a peer-body system to ask for extra help. This is a preventive measure developed by a committed and informed learner (Interview script, May 5, 2008).

5.2 RESOURCES AND HANDS-ON EXPERIENCE (LEARNERS)

It is one thing to encounter obstacles in life, and another to be able to overcome these obstacles. The success of students is in their ability to devise means to overcome their academic challenges. The information gathered from the participants indicated that they encountered similar obstacles. Thompson concludes, “the West African system does not appreciate the substantial potential that higher education offers in contributing to the countries’ industrial development” (Thompson, (1977, p. 96). The manufacturing industries are neglected and non-utilized, and conversely the abundant human resources produced by the Polytechnics and Universities are under-utilized by the industries and the State.

According to Teni, her current nursing program is structured to cater to needs that make it relevant to face shocks as one prepares to practice in the field. To this effect, the university had put in place a field experience program for the students. She said:

They have clinical placements structured for us, and other range of knowledge driven structures. We were made to do ‘shadowing’ so that we can bear with frustrations. We have a ‘state of the art studio’ so that we can actually have technological ‘hands-on’ practice with guinea pigs that have not been used before (Interview script, May 5, 2008).

She further explained the state of the art studio is located off campus in one of the main general hospitals where students are able to merge practically what they learned theoretically in the classroom.

Vero has similar things to say but from a different setting. Vero made an analogy to the multipurpose instruments available in Canada but are were also common in the affluent Nigerian society. In Vero's view, she posits:

You saw and used a lot of these instruments, all because the three doctors that founded 'Eko hospital' had their first degrees in Nigeria but studied for their further degrees outside Nigeria. Actually, I did not have problems with this aspect. Where I worked for instance in a Nigerian hospital, we had a CT scan, we had a mammogram, we had a Cancer unit and had trained nurses for the use of such equipment. We also have an Intensive Care Unit (ICU) and Cardiac monitoring machine and stimulants to mention a few. Hence I saw some of these machines here in Canada, and it was not new to me. The only thing that was new to me was the 'code blue' cases, which I had no knowledge about and had to learn it from others (Interview script, May 5, 2008).

Tommy and Skemeh had similar views to share on resources and hands-on experience ventures. They both stated that: here in Canada there are a lot of resources at your disposal that one can use which we don't have access to in West Africa. Instructors here are very helpful and are willing to help you to achieve your goal as a student. Secondly, the schools in Canada are good and they have a strong desire to help students succeed. I know some of the students' may have difficulties, achieving their goals and hence the schools have part-time students who come to assist you on your own scheduled times as resources persons.

Skemeh puts it this way:

Science is almost like Mathematics. The way we do math back home there are some of the questions one does not have to use calculators. Some of these questions you have to use your brain to do your calculations. But here in Canada everything is there for your delight. There is easy access to facilities and resources. Even I remember some of my exams were open book exams, which I found it to be very interesting, which never happen in my West African background of education (Interview script, May 10, 2008).

5.3 EDUCATORS' AND LEARNERS' CULTURAL DIFFERENCES

Hofstede concludes that what is acceptable in one culture may not be equally acceptable in another (Hofstede, 1991). There are various approaches to the way things are done and ways words are pronounced from one setting to another. Campbell (1988) mentioned that “these differences often led to unintended conflicts such as those that often arise during intercultural encounters and which happen although nobody wants them and many become sufferers as a result” (cited in Hofstede, 1991, p. 208). Each of the participants describes these conflicts differently, although some relate to one another. The fact that one’s intuition in a particular discipline does not measure up is not a criterion for the impossibility to strive higher, as Freire puts it. Paraphrasing a comment according to Freire, *what individuals must not do is to stop at the instinct level of our emotions, feelings and intuitions* (Freire, 2005, p.49 – 54). Teni and Professor May held similar views regarding emotions in section 4.4 and 4.5, chapter four when both explained that individual West African science students who have immigrated to Canada to do further studies should work to overcome emotions by facing the challenges; this inculcates self-competency and cultural competence. Tommy emphasized on differences in competence, saying:

In my case my background into science in Ghana, West Africa was very minimal. I didn’t have much background into *science* before I went into Georgian College. But as I can say the little knowledge about science that I had by then was only about one tenth in high school. That was just learning periodic tables, in Chemistry (Interview script, April 27, 2008).

Tommy also dwelled on language variation in pronunciation and sound (phonetics). He said:

What I focus on was the language (language barrier). You know the way I will say some things may turn the teachers off or they would not understand what I mean. My accent makes it difficult from the beginning. You may say potassium in a different way or helium and may sound differently to somebody and they may ask: “*what did you say?*” “*Pardon me?*” It is quite frustrating to keep repeating the same things over and over again for months before making headway (Interview script, April 27, 2008).

Tommy explained further that if professors’ can overcome the “cultural stigma” a little bit, then that will be very helpful. He further speculated that there are so many instructors who are very

good, and helpful. But yet still a couple of them are of the attitude that ‘if I cannot understand you then I cannot help you.’ Britzman narrates that each person has their own way of getting ideas across. She writes: “I may have an idea about what I want to communicate, but consideration must be given, knowing that other people are coming from so many different places with so many thoughts in their heads” (Britzman, 2003, p. 90).

Teni holds similar views on cultural variance:

Due to the diverse cultural background of the Canadian society one tends to be more understanding and tolerant to the other. For instance one thing that might be accepted in my culture in Nigeria may not be accepted in Canada. Secondly, language was another issue to battle with in my day-to-day activities. Sometimes our professors’ would speak so fast that one could not pick all the words contained in their sentences and makes it difficult to understand the message they were conveying to us (Interview script, May 5, 2008).

Supporting studies reveal similar results for considering the interest of the ‘other’ on account of feeling and respect. Levinas states that educational sustainability is possible when the voices of the ‘other’ are not played down (cited in Silverstone 2003).

Teaching and learning is a reciprocal process and both learners and educators should complement each other. Freire and Vygotsky posit “learner’s come into the classroom with enough knowledge based on their lived experiences” (Cited in Wink, 2005, p. 30 & Freire, 2005). Vero describes this, stating: “The professors here should not think they know everything. There are things they do not know, which we know and there are things that they know that we do not know, because of cultural differences (cultural variance).” There should be freedom to fail in expression of views and knowledge so that perfection can take place rather than the old fashioned “banking system” where the teacher knows it all and others who do not present essays and quantitative solutions to problems as the teacher wants it are doom to fail.

Relationships are vital for students to achieve at all levels of their academic pursuits. Skemeh described how some professors might take a student’s shyness to be disrespect. He said:

In West Africa the relationship between students and the professor is very rigid. Students do not joke with professors. Relationships are very official type and both students and professors are very careful but here in North America, both professors and students flow freely.

Skemeh further explained this by advising that:

Professors should know that if they have graduate student from West Africa and that students seem not to get closer to them, they should be aware and know that it is due to that cultural difference and that the professor should not take it that the student is not getting along with them (Interview script, May 10, 2008).

Rather, he encourages professors to offer careful consideration and reflection to such student's values as their culture. This poignant advice has ethical issues embedded in it. It is obvious that the problems associated with education are not just pedagogical problems. They are also partly political, ethical, and financial problems (Freire, 2005). That is one aspect of culture shock that we go through as foreign students from West Africa, due to our background training. Studies point to cultural differences between educators and learners in education and its consequences. Callender (1997), found that particular attention to cultural styles, and, in particular, non-verbal behavior can operate in direct opposition to an educational institutional authority structure. This, she states, "oftentimes results in negative teacher perceptions about Black students in general" (Callender, 1997, p. 64).

5.4 CULTURAL CAPITAL AND VOICE IN ACCOUNTABILITY

Not all of the participants had the feeling that the West African science students' as well as their professors needed to be more accountable for themselves and the science programs they studied or taught. With regards to accountability, Teni pointed out the abundance of resources and how professors are accountable for whatever they do because they are evaluated at the end of each course. She recounts her enjoyment as regards to the handouts that were given for free at lectures, including resources such as the audiovisual aids, the availability of computers, which made learning much easier. This practice was uncommon to her in a West African educational

setting. According to her, what is available in Canadian education system is also available in the Nigerian education system, but these materials are only found in some of the upper class schools, where only the affluent can afford them. The teachers in Nigeria (similar trend is observed in the Ghanaian and other West African States) do not work hard enough during the normal school schedule. They rather prefer to do a poor job teaching during the normal school run and then engage students' in part time or after school for extra classes for monetary gains. Previous research by Michael Apple revealed that the private sector of education has failed the education system tremendously due to the stigma attached to money making rather than seeking the progress of learners. Apple writes: There is a widespread argument that trade liberalization, in the interest of efforts to promote private provision of education, inevitably treats education as a market commodity, thereby undermining academic traditions of free inquiry and university autonomy (Apple et. al., 2005). In the Canadian educational system as Teni puts it, professors are accountable for whatever they do because they are evaluated at the end of each course. In the West African system we see too much autonomy given to professors, which has become abusive (personal observation). Vero summed it in the phrase "we have to compliment each other" to indicate that both the educator/learner has the onerous responsibility of being accountable to themselves and to the larger community. Teaching and learning should be a two-sided process and a form of resource sharing.

5.5 MARGINALIZED AND DISCONNECTED

In a multicultural system there are bound to be some practices that alienate others based on race, class, sex, and knowledge level. The Canadian higher education system is not an exception. Some foreign students depending on the country they come from are less experienced with the use of computer and other technology. For these reasons aspects of emotion with regards to technology, environment and segregation act as barriers to these students with such background.

The United Nation's Millennium Goal states, "Inclusiveness in a learning community is where other learners are not alienated. According to Lewis (2006, p. 3), inclusiveness in learning promotes sustainability in education." *What are some of the survival skills needed to help these groups of students succeed in the transition process in their academic and social pursuits and over the probability of dropping out from the respective programs?* This also answers Dzama's question of, *what may be the root causes of the attainment of poor marks by Black students - Dzama (1999)?* The participants angrily expressed and discussed the way marks have been awarded to them, even if they have received higher grades than their white counter-parts with whom they studied (Teni, 5 May, 2008 & Vero, 4 May, 2008). With regards to segregation, Teni stated: "They should be aware of their biases towards us so that they can be non-judgmental and non-prejudice. They should be open and have that spirit of learning new things about other peoples' culture" (Interview script, May 5, 2008).

Vero mentioned how she was rejected by a group of her classmates, when she wanted to join their study group (Interview script, May 4, 2008). Such act is considered a "flawed sorting mechanism of selecting who can be part of a student study group" (Hinchey, 2004, p.103). I faced similar cultural capital separation in both my teacher education and physics graduate studies in the past from fellow white students. I recall situations that I asked to join a study group and only to see the other students' look at each other's face and making a gesture that connoted 'no way.' Solomon posits that to discriminate against subordinate groups based on their putative attributes is to deny their equitable participation (Solomon, 2003). I add that it is the bond and affiliation that the members of that group may have with each other which leads them to see the 'other' as not a true reflection of their kind, hence the rejection. Such encounters result in anxiety and stress. Hones (1997) cites Dewey's notion of education as experiential. Dewey advises that when learners engage with others of different ethnicities, social classes, and language

backgrounds, students learn to become community builders with their limitless experiences and sense of self (cited in Solomon, 2003). Vero felt that joining a group would stretch her limits of experience but her efforts were thwarted (Interview script, May 4, 2008). Thwarted because the group felt she does not fit in their class or on the contrary, they felt intimidated by her personality. It could also be the group had a mindset of an inferiority complex toward her for being Black, an act reminiscent of stereotyping in educational institutions both among students and educators.

CHAPTER SIX

6.0 INFERENCES

Although each of the participants' information conveys the truth of each individual's personal life story, adding "tit-bits" in the complexities of my own experience in Canadian Higher Education would help in the explanations. Furnham described four variables that help to explain the relationship of how sojourners movements affect their psychological adjustment (well-being). One of these variables is fatalism, defined as "the perception of general self-efficacy and the control over events in one's life." Fatalism, according to Furnham and Bochner (1986), generalizes the expectation that outcomes are determined by forces such as "powerful others," luck, or fate. Fatalism is also stated as the belief that all events are predetermined and therefore inevitable (Barber, 1998). Furnham and Bochner posit that fatalism implies events cannot be changed and that people ought to be submissive to events. Rather, I find the meaning of the term to be a generalized expectation that outcomes are contingent of one's own behaviour. The disparities between two countries contribute to the severity of other aspect of life psychological disturbance, for example depression (Furnham et. al., 1986). In my situation, when accusations were leveled against me by the "powerful other," in this case, an educator, the result yielded a change in the psychological well being of my person. The external consequences to learning motivation contributed to cutting short my career and aspiration to pursue physics. These stories can sometimes seem "distant and separate from our own – destinies to be shaped by forces beyond our control" (Furnham et. al., 1986, p. 168). Although I do not feel segregation was at play in my bitter encounter but such acts constitute segregation rooted in alienation and isolation in this regards. In the final analysis in this research, I cannot resolve a conclusion due to the small number of participants interviewed. Also, the setting of the people interviewed only included

individuals living in the Greater Toronto Area and that make this findings less conclusive. The selected locality makes the views of the selected individuals to be too polarized to conclude on the experiences of 'WASS.' However, the analysis and discussions of the findings indicates that the deficits in experiences are due to both individual and institutional contexts.

Patricia Hinchey is correct in her reference to the Bell Curve (Hinchey, 2004). She discussed the continual existence of an inherent inferiority complex in the many mindsets towards African Americans of which West Africans are no exception. Hinchey states many Whites claim that academic standards will fall when African Americans begin attending certain schools. Stated differently, she states:

Research has indicated that many teachers and administrators start easing standards and expectations downward when the population changes, based on their assumption about what learners who look or sound a certain way will be interested in or capable of (Hinchey, 2004, p. 110) and also (Teni, Interview script, May 5, 2008).

Checking such nuances will be difficult, but that is the surest way to overcome the cultural capital others have regarding the abilities and capabilities of others. Cultural capital is the ways of behaving, talking, acting, thinking, and moving among other things (Wink, 2005). Regards cultural capital and voice in accountability, my observation in North America educational institutions, it is believed that one has to communicate very directly and concisely to succeed. Three of the participants in this study mentioned racism as a factor that plays into the experiences of West African science students in Canadian Higher Educational institutions. Vero for instance stated that educators are helpful in the Canadian system, but they should realize that there are some things they know which we (West African students) do not know and vice versa. Teni, on the other hand, advised that some educators in the Canadian Higher Educational institutions should check their biases and know that everybody carries with them some rich knowledge experience from somewhere. The above explanations are situated on educators' and learners' cultural differences. Departure from the above individuals' shared experiences on cultural

competence, cultural variance, cultural baggage, and individual differences, counteracts the notions of Hofstede's (1991) and Riley's (2005). The two authors insufficiently explained 'cultural baggage' term but on the other hand made a positive case of argument to the quest for "blended education that gives hope" (Freire, 2005, p. 75) and (Hinchey, 2004; Solomon, 2003; Wink, 2005). Nevertheless, the tone of these authors on cultural baggage stands in marked contrast to their anti-cultural competence and self-efficacy fusillades. The voice of minorities are over-shadowed in a cultural capitalist society and according to Hinchey (2004), living in someone else's "world of knowing" indicates low self-esteem (Maslow, 1943).

6.1 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR POLICY AND PRACTICE

Are the problems they encounter individual or institutional or both? What future directions could be put in place to further enhance their chances and interest in pursuing science in Canada? To answer these questions is to look at how marginalized and disconnectedness has shattered the educational-social strengths and survival of the Black minority group. In a future plan of remedy, I recommend that the hiring process in the professorial rank should ensure that it reflect the students' population. This should not be considered at the university and college level only but throughout the entire educational hierarchy in the Canadian Educational system. I have observed the trend and find it to be such an unwelcome idea of practice to leave it where we are. Neglect of this suggestion would mean more marginalization and disconnections of some minorities, in particular Blacks in the Canadian society. I believe that if there are equal proportions of West African professors in the system, it will help curtail the indifferences that arise due to cultural variance. If there are as many Black professors as there are professors from other nations in Canadian universities, they can comprise a committee of matters affecting West African science students. Also I suggest that educators/professors should take sabbatical leaves of

absence to visit and understudy the West African Education system. People of the same culture know how they feel and how to resolve issues they encounter either as a group or as individuals. It is my belief that taking such study tours will further enlighten foreign educators to be better equipped to help West African science students to succeed in their higher education.

I also recommend that professors who supervise/teach West African (research) science students should offer them more hands-on laboratory work in the case of the pure and applied sciences, to cushion them for experiential scientific research. Though Skill base science instruction (SBSI) is messy and financially appealing, but it offers the best opportunity for life skills acquisition as Kabba proposed (Kabba, 2005). This motivational factor would boost self-confidence, self-esteem, and the achievements of students. It is vital to implement effective teaching profiles that highlight culturally responsive relationship building, which will support Freirian's speculation of the need for nurturing caring classroom freedom, practices rooted in eco-justice, sustainability and open scholarly atmosphere for both educators and learners (Bishop et. al, 2007). This would help both educators and learners to become co-constructors and co-authors of knowledge (Florence & Yore, 2004 and Freire, 2005).

The experiences of West African science students as well as other foreign students in a new higher educational system such as institutions in Canada should not be seen as simple trajectories as depicted by AX, in figure 'A' in chapter 5. Those individual students whose situations may be keen due to individual differences may be depicted as curves TC and TB, but the majority overcomes these barriers as shown by the curve TA. These individual and collective student experiences are linked to many social, economic and geographical factors. A major factor in the underachievement of Black learners is that "they experience inordinate ambivalence and affective dissonance with regard to academic effort and success" (Callender, 1997, p. 58). Examples of the dissonance include unwarranted comments on assignments scripts upon return and poor judgment

in the award of marks. Such occurrences set the tone for emotional trauma in new science students in the Canadian higher educational system. My physics assignment scripts are testimonials to such dissonance (appendix B). I view some of the words in the comment lines as condescending rather than presenting advice for growth. They portray acts reminiscent of disrespect for others' methods and ways of representing solutions to questions, whether qualitative or quantitative, if the approaches do not look similar to what educators preferred. On the other hand, should the solutions of students look so close to what the educator expect, must it call for suspicion and questioning? Thijs and Van den Berg (1995) are quoted as saying that "the scientific worldview represents a foreign subculture in all countries and cultures" (cited in Dzama, 1999, p. 401). Hence, decisions for pre-judgment could lead, to some extent, marginalizing and career-ending on the part of students if no careful and comprehensive considerations are given based on the background of the new science student, in particular those from Sub-Saharan West Africa. In another form to answer the question, "Are the problems WASS encounter individual or institutional or both?" I suggest the institution of a 'program of action to mitigate the social costs of adjustment' (PAMSCAD) to offer these students some financial boost, at the higher educational level. Some personal acquaintances expressed to me they receive no financial assistance from anywhere. They explained how they starved themselves on the little surplus research grant left on their scholarships after paying their school fees.

6.2 FUTURE DIRECTIONS RECOMMENDED FOR STUDENTS SUCCESS

What recommendations could be drawn from the study of the experiences of West African science students in Canadian higher educational institutions?

A valuable solution to help West African science students' dilemmas is developing critical "lifelong learning" habits and self-sacrifice learning attitudes. Committed educators and learners

cannot allow pre-judgment to dictate the way to look at issues and events in one another. The fact is that being pre-judgmental is not divine in how other students - based on their background - are handled (Hinchey, 2004). I am reiterating an earlier point made about how I was accused wrongly in an assignment I presented in Solid State Physics and later was exonerated on account that there was nothing wrong with the way I presented my solutions. Although I was asked to put behind the trauma, I have endured but the setbacks continued to linger on. The decision was pre-judgmental and wrong to carry a student's text scripts to the higher authority for scrutiny while it could have been done in an atmosphere of trust, respect, and confidence.

The acceptances of many practices that constitute the way things are, find place similar to the endorsement of goals in critical theory (Hinchey, 2004). 'WASS' should place emphasis on learning about the host country culture to function effectively. Freedom, openness, and acceptance of others' knowledge in classrooms/lecture rooms constitute motivation (Harrow, 1972 and Psychological Review, 50). "Variations in students' linguistic and cultural backgrounds influence results in several ways that have nothing to do with intelligence or ability" (Hinchey, 2004, p. 108). It is important for those who travel elsewhere for academic purposes to adopt and adapt bicultural strategies to promote success. Macfadyen and Schonberger (2006) explain the adaptation skills that new students need to adopt to have a smooth academic transition, making reference to blurring boundaries (Macfadyen & Schonberger 2006). Overcoming the use of high-tech tools to survive the acculturation in the transition process demands that the student put in extra effort to overcome the technology gap (chapter 2).

How can the West African science students' (WASS) yield their full academic potential through motivation? Some of the interviewees indicated that the feedbacks and comments on assignment and test scripts they received were demoralizing and did little to motivate them. This was exemplified in one of the participant's dialogue when she pointed out that some educators in

the Canadian system should check their biases and nuances (Interviewed script, May 5, 2008). The comment made by Riley (2005), explain that “the cultural change of which sometimes the cultural beliefs of the receiving group could be undoubtedly harmful to learning or excessively discriminatory” is valid (Riley, 2005, p. 8). I believe Riley’s point is connected both to the receiving institutions and the sending institutions. Educators in Canada should realize that a lived culture is difficult to neglect at a go. Patience and understanding about where individuals are coming from will help to cement the good relationships that need to be nurtured. Educators will need to adopt long-range planning in how to disseminate lessons to meet the various needs of adult learners. Also, African universities will need radical systematic instruction in the form of inquiry (skill) based learning of science in the classroom (Farmer and Farrell, 1980 & Kabba, 2005).

What are some of the experiences of West African science students in Canada, and how are these differences connected to discourses and discussions that take place in the field of higher education? The response by one of the informants interviewed points out that some professors should check their nuances and biases. This statement corresponds to the assertion by Hofstede that professors are human and indifferent. Some of their biased thinking and writing is based on their “experiences of material representation” (Hofstede, 1997, p. 146). At some point the minority group feel marginalized and disconnected; by the way such materials are represented in one way or another.

One of the participants, Skemeh, highlighted the official nature of the relationships between the professor and student in West Africa culture and how this relationship dictates the pace in teaching and learning. The census conducted by Hofstede revealed inequalities between students and professors that reflect Skemeh’s view of “official relationships” (Hofstede, 1997, & Interview script, May 10, 2008). Power distance is very large in the African context and this

relationship makes it difficult for West African students to pursue effective in-class dialogue with their professors. This is attributed to our ways of life (cultural practices). The power distance has also made the 'banking model' in education more acceptable practice within the African educational context. Educators are considered the main resource and custodians of knowledge and therefore changing this course will be considered rebellion. The theme "resources and hands-on experiences of learners" answers whether *the problems students encountered are to be looked as individual or institutional or both?* To acquire hands-on experience is to practice with the laboratory equipments/apparatus. In most African educational laboratory settings, it is such that most of the Higher Educational institutions (until recently) have minimum or old equipments to cater for the students' population pursuing programs in the sciences. To answer the part that deals with the individual problem, I urge African students to open up and take nothing for granted in their higher academic pursuits and be aware that seeking, questioning, and participating bring understanding. We (students) can benefit from our professors only when we have done our own further research on topics we are studying rather than depending completely on them as the connoisseurs (authority) of knowledge. The stakes are too high and I advocate for blended learning and teaching styles necessary and imperative for students to adopt and adapt to new institutional praxis, using their previous experiences as mediation tools, both home and abroad. The students should aim at focusing on and building upon knowledge through active learning (content with process). There is the need to develop the abilities and disposition that investigate the needed scientific process skills. Florence and Yore assertion of encouraging students to learn like scientist resonates in these points (Florence & Yore, 2004). Shymansky, Hedges and Woodworth (1990) advocate a similar notion of allowing students to learn the way scientist practice science to gain understanding and develop scientific process skills.

What are some of the survival skills needed to help these groups of students succeed in the transition process in their academic and social pursuits and overcome the probability of dropping out from the respective programs? The root cause of attaining poor marks in science particularly is rooted in the speculation given by Dzama (1999) and the explanations to this are in two fold. First, the fact that few Blacks pursue pure science programs should be looked upon, as a matter of interest and not to conclude that Black science students deserve only poor marks. I see the “pedagogy of care” missing and it is one of the many causes, leading to a lot of West African science students and others dropping from their science programs. Educators must be open and caring in understanding learners of West African descent, considering their background and the linear modes in which they are taught in science. The second reason for explaining this scenario is the little familiarity by WASSs’ with some sophisticated scientific laboratory instruments/equipment. These two causes above explain the theme of “cultural capital and voice in accountability.” For some students, this generates in them a feeling of inferiority complex in exploring topics, even when the chance is made available to learn new things in familiar discipline.

6.3 IMPLICATION FOR THE RESEARCH AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Throughout this study, various themes have emerged which have implications for furthering what constitutes the experiences of West African science students (WASS) in the Canadian Higher (tertiary) Educational institutions. These include pedagogical issues that evolve teaching and learning styles of both educators and learners respectively. Others include disconnectedness, as well as language barrier and achievement. Differences in pedagogy, due to educators’ and learners’ cultural differences, make it difficult for certain students to swiftly adapt to new styles of teaching and learning in the Canadian system. These students also find it difficult to cope with

the various study groups in their programs because of how they are viewed by members of ‘those study groups’ as inferior and thus not accepted (personal communication, April 19, 2007). The hegemony of the dominant group to control knowledge and literacy is rooted in the theme “cultural capital and voice in accountability.” In my observation, I seldom find language barrier as the root cause and not necessarily on the content of knowledge level. Wink (2005) defines hegemony as “the domination of one group over another with partial consent of the dominant group” (Wink, 2005, p. 45). These difficulties including language barriers bring disconnectedness owing to how others understand the self-expression of some students based on the varying ethnographic background knowledge, as mentioned earlier in chapter one.

Inference from the interview with Vero thus answers the question; *Are there some paradigm shifts that take place in the culture of teaching and learning pedagogies that have affected their capabilities for a sound academic performance and how can they be motivated to yield their full academic potential?* Tables 3.1 and 3.2, offers quiet an extensive background and work-related experiences of the participants and explain their egos as “committed learners.” Unfortunately, the experiences from their native countries before immigrating have not been sufficient to fetch them their dream occupations in Canada. Studying in two different educational environments is like a crucible where learners’ and educators’ are tested and challenged everyday to stand out for the best. The findings in this research are purposefully two fold. First is to help science educators in Canada and West African during disseminating educational information in their curriculum to embrace flexibility. Knowing a bit of the cultural background of one’s students will help groom them for growth academically and socially. Secondly, is to inform institutions, educators and learners of the need to value mutual care and respect in a learning community.

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APPENDIX A

Investigator: Good afternoon, it is nice meeting you in your residence. This meeting is purposefully interviewing you regards my Major Research Project (MRP) thesis on the topic: *West African Canadian Science Students' Post-secondary Experiences of Science Education in Canada and in West Africa: The Coherence between Teaching and Learning*. The first question I want to ask you is 'can you tell me about your experience in learning science in West Africa?'

Thank you so much for the privilege for having you in my house to have this discussion. Yes! I studied science and also thought science in West Africa before coming to Canada. My experience with in science in West Africa is that because of limited resources, the learning of science is more of theory and abstract. The laboratory work was so limited and so many of the equipment that I knew were mentioned in the textbook but I never saw them but learned more about them. I can describe them and their function, but saw them neither did I touch them. I am glad that I had the opportunity to come over to experience another side of science.

Investigator: *Can you tell me about your experiences in learning science in North America specifically the type of program you studied and what are some of the pertinent experiences?*

Okay! Had my Master's degree in Aquaculture as well as my Philosophy degree in Molecular genetics all in North America. The first difference was that because they were graduate studies there was a lot of laboratory work. The laboratory work was to augment whatever we learnt in class. That brought many of the theories to practice. There were a lot of calculations, there were a lot of equipments to play around with and so that's the first difference. The second difference is that in my undergraduate when I was learning science there were no available computers at that time. Now that I am doing my graduate studies, there were a lot of computers around and therefore it is a different ballgame. I mean I have access to computers so therefore I can literally do so many things that during my undergraduate era in West Africa I had to do things manually. So there is a different ballgame but eh! I have had the experience to taste both sides.

Investigator: *Can you enlighten further, as to what the calculations in the molecular genetics study meant?*

Yes! I can. In West Africa whenever we are given a problem to solve we are advice to show every calculation step that was taken to arrive at the final answer. And that is what has guided me to this far. I make sure when ever I am doing any calculations, I follow he logical steps and to arrive at the final answer because teachers in West Africa basically look at the step taken to arrive at one's result. Hence immediately you get the final answer wrong, they can look at your logical steps and give you partial credit. In North America, on the contrary (Technology), I have studied and taught science here, but because most of the kids here in Canada have sophisticated calculators and that entire staff, they key in all

the figures into the calculator and they end up writing the last two steps and that is it. That is one of the big difference I see in problem solving based on sophisticated calculators.

Investigator: *Do notice any difference in problem solving and what are these? You have talk about this in the quantitative (mathematical way), can you talk about it in the qualitative (essay writing) briefly?*

In West Africa, when asked to write any type of essay, we were taught to start with the introduction, then the objective and main body and conclusion. In North America, it is very similar except that most of the time students don't take the time to write the introduction. Rather they go straight to the point and sometimes too they list the factors for instance and state just one sentence about the topic. But whilst in West Africa, you are told to list the factors with regards a topic, explain, and give examples. That is the difference I see in the two systems.

Investigator: *Can you elaborate on some of the challenges you encountered in North America and how did you overcome them?*

Okay! There were few challenges that one has to do with you know flying from West Africa with a temperature of about $28^{\circ}C$ into $-5^{\circ}C$ in North America. So that was my first experience for me to battle with the cold and get settled. I also arrived at the time that school was in full session (had re-opened) and I was late in arrival. So I had a week behind to catch up with different environment but my supervising professor understood me and we agreed on catching up with my classes (lectures) with no major laboratory work during that time span. That went on very well with me. Another major issue was with technology. I didn't have enough computer skills before I came in here. So when I was here and realize so many things had to be done on the computer, it was a big challenge. There are many of the software's I have never heard of their names but because I had to use them I had to spend extra time to learn them and which, eventually helped me. That which helped me was taking extra time to learn the things that I did not know but were helpful in achieving success.

I also had friends who helped me in that area. With regards to friends and supported family members, when I came in first I had a friend from West Africa, who gave me one-on-one orientation about had to succeed in the department. He gave me all the details of what I needed to succeed. He briefed me on the sequence at which I should take my courses such that I meet all the pre-requisite before I take my main courses. Also we had a lot of time with my professor because initially he had problem with my language but with time we were able to catch up with each other and we were free flowing in a matter of few months, you know. I remember when I first arrived my initial two major courses were with my supervising professor. He was always observing my English and writing styles and he was impressed finally. He thought my writings were different but they made a lot of sense to him.

Investigator: *Did you come here with your family and if so or not how were you able to make it?*

I came here one year ahead before my wife and kids joined me and when they came they were very supportive. They were helped in so many situations in terms of errands and that helped me to do other

academic stuff. That aside did not mean I neglected my responsibility as a father. I was able to meet all those challenges and was able to take care of my family.

Investigator: *In your capacity as grandaunt and in your capacity as a community dweller, what advice would you give to West African Canadian science students and others who have migrated here to do science?*

In the first place the purpose of education is to transmit culture. Though it is the same science but the emphasis in West Africa is totally different from the emphasis in North America with respect to Canada. Therefore when one migrate to study in North America, since there is a shift in emphasis, one has to devote much time to find out which area he/she is deficient and make up for it. For instance find out the pre-requisites of all the courses you are registered to take and meet them before registering. One have to study vehemently since it is a different ballgame altogether. Since one is coming in new with all the challenges, it is advice that whenever you are given a project work start work on it as early as possible forestall delay which will course you to rush to submit your assignment with poor proof reading. Complete your assignment early, refine it, and retune it before the final deadline. Most North American students leave their assignments till the last minute. I will not advice this practice to new science students from West Africa. Start early, work harder at it a piece of it at a time, ask questions, fine tune it and I will trust that it will work better for you. That is what I did and it worked for me.

Investigator: *What advice if any would you give to the professors' who handle us herein North America in the sciences? Looking at cultural differences?*

In West Africa the relationship between students and the professor is very rigid. Students do not joke with professors'. It is very official type of relationship and both students and professors are very careful but here in North America, both professors' and students' flow freely. Sometimes we see professors and students at the pub drinking and charting together and doing all sorts of things together. In West Africa and in particular Ghana, the relationship is very official. That is one of the first cultural shock that one from West Africa will face. Professor's should know that if one have a graduate student from West Africa and that students seem not to get closer to them they should be aware and know that it is due to that cultural difference and is a cultural shock and that the professor should not take it that the student does not like him or her but rather take it as the person's culture. Another thing I will advice professor's is that whenever they have science students' from West Africa countries, because they had limited laboratory work in their respective science training, I will ask that they be assigned more laboratory work so they can build the pre-requisite skills to achieve their full potential.

Investigator: Thank you very much and it's been a pleasure talking with you.

Thank you.

APPENDIX B

APPENDIX C

Research Informed Consent

Date:

My name is Appiah-Odame, Eric. K, and my Major Research Project thesis topic for the Masters degree study is '*International science students' post-secondary experiences of science education in Canada and in West Africa: the coherence between teaching and learning*'.

The purpose of the research is to study the experiences of West African Canadian science students in Canada and in West Africa. You will be engaged in an interview between forty-five minutes to an hour, which will be taped recorded and not videotaped.

My interview will give you an opportunity to reflect on your experiences in your field of study and how they may serve as a guide to other West African Canadian students in the Canadian educational system. The interview will provide opportunities for me to learn and benefit from your experience and to reflect on some of the details of the everyday paradigm shifts in the pedagogical process for future adaptation. I will also be used to inform other new West African science students in Canada about some of the adaptation skills necessary while studying in Canadian higher educational institutions.

Your participation in the study is completely voluntary and you may choose to stop participating at any time and your data will be destroyed. Your decision not to volunteer will not influence the nature of your relationship with York University or other group associated with this project either now, or in the future. All information you supply during the research will be held in confidence and unless you specifically indicate your consent, your name will not appear in any report or publication of the research. Only pseudonyms will be used in compiling the MRP thesis. Your data will be safely stored in a locked facility. Confidentiality will be provided to the fullest extent possible by law.

Should the need arise for questions or concerns about the research in general, feel free to contact either; professor Steve Alsop @ telephone 416-736- 2100 ext 20665 and email @ salsop@edu.yorku.ca or the student researcher @ telephone 905-787-0048 and e-mail esarah@yorku.ca; at the faculty of education, Keele campus. This research project has been reviewed by the Human Participant Research Committee of the Faculty of Education and conforms to the standards of the Canadian tri-council research ethics guidelines. If you have any questions about participation in the study, please contact the Graduate Program office research ethics, 309 York lanes, York University @ telephone 416-736-5914.

Legal Rights and Signatures:

I _____, consent to participate in the research interviews conducted by the student researcher Appiah-Odame Eric. K. I have understood the nature of this project and wish to participate. I am not waiving any legal rights by signing this form. My signature below indicates my consent

Participant

Date _____

Eric.K. Appiah-Odame
Principal investigator

Date June 2009